

Supplemental Material for:

Fluid-implicit particle solvers in video gaming engine provide new perspectives in hydroinformatics

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1 BLENDER WORKFLOW

The following sections the creation and optimization of a Blender model for its use with Unreal Engine and its Niagara Fluids plugin, as well as OpenFOAM. Comprehensive tutorials for using Blender can be found in the official software documentation ([BlenderContributors 2023](#)).

1.1 Creation of a Blender Model

Both the PIC/FLIP simulation in Unreal Engine and the grid-based simulation in OpenFOAM used the same Blender model. The following workflow was implemented in Blender to create the elements of the VSF. Due to the complexity of the VSF, the workflow only illustrates the exemplary creation of a simple channel with a vertical wooden cylinder placed in the center of the channel.

- i. Start with a new (blank) project in Blender and create an empty working space. Structural elements that are available as STL files can be directly imported (*File > Import > Stl (.stl)*). Other elements like the compound structure of the VSF needed to be built from scratch, analogous to the following for the simple channel with a wooden cylinder.
- ii. Elements to be built from scratch are created in *Object Mode*, by selecting a type of element (e.g., 2d *Plane*, illustrated in Fig. S-1).

Fig. S- 1. Create a new *Plane* object in Blender.

- 17 iii. The size and location of the new object (here, *Plane*) are set during creation (see Fig. S-2 a),
 18 or later in *Edit Mode*.
- 19 iv. To modify an object (i.e., the *Plane*), that is, edit vertices, edges, or faces, use *Edit Mode*
 20 (Tab key or top menu). For instance, the *Transform* panel (see Fig. S-2 b) in *Edit Mode*
 enabled us to modify the coordinates of mouse-selected vertices.

21 **Fig. S- 2.** Element modification in Blender: (a) settings for the element size and location, and (b)
 the *Transform* panel for modifying vertices.

- 22 v. 3d elements, like the wall of the channel are created by extruding the (long) edges of the
 23 plane *Plane* (see Fig. S-3). To this end, a long *Edge* of the *Plane* is mouse-selected, and
 24 pressing the E key opens the *Extrude* command. Pressing the Z key enabled us to extrude
 25 the edge in the vertical Z-direction, by dragging the edge to the desired height (2 m in
 26 Fig. S-3). The coordinates can alternatively be adjusted using the *Extrude Region and*
 27 *Move* panel. Repeating the *Extrude* operation on the opposite edge creates a long channel
 28 with an open inlet and outlet.
 29 To define inlet and outlet faces, the four vertices formed by the extruded long edges are
 30 selected. With the four vertices highlighted, pressing the F key formed a face (Fig. S-4).
 This operation was repeated at the outlet.

31 **Fig. S- 3.** Extrusion (by 2 m) of one of the long edges of the *Plane* to create a channel wall.

- 32 vi. To place another element in the present structure, re-enable *Object Mode*. For example,
 33 Fig. S-5 features the placement of a *Cylinder Mesh*, where vertices, radius, depth, and
 34 location can be adapted.

Fig. S- 4. Highlighting the four end vertices of the two extruded edges and pressing the F key creates a face at the channel inlet.

35 vii. Subdivision into materials facilitates assigning characteristics to particular elements (e.g.,
 36 friction) and boundary conditions (in OpenFOAM). For instance, the following materials
 37 and boundaries apply to the simple channel:

- 38 • Bottom boundary (gravel-bed);
- 39 • Cylinder (wood);
- 40 • Side walls (concrete);
- 41 • Inlet (air);
- 42 • Outlet (air); and
- 43 • Top boundary (air).

44 To subdivide the channel structure into these materials, select the entire compound structure
 45 in the *Scene Collection* panel (right side of the window), then switch back to *Edit Mode*. With
 46 *Face Select* enabled, singular faces can be highlighted (e.g., the *Bottom* boundary, highlighted
 47 in Fig. S-6), and then separated by pressing the P key. This activates the *Separate* context menu
 48 that allows for converting the selected face into a new *Mesh*, which subsequently occurs in the

Fig. S- 5. Example for adding a *Mesh > Cylinder* to the structure (in *Object Mode*).

Fig. S- 6. Elements of the exemplary channel, including a bottom boundary (highlighted), cylinder, side walls, inlet, outlet, and top boundary. The bottom-right corner shows the *Scene Collection* panel after the separation of all channel elements.

49 *Scene Collection* panel. This process is applied repetitively until all elements of the structure
 50 appear in the *Scene Collection* panel. To simultaneously separate multiple faces, hold down the
 51 **Shift** key during the selection.

52 In the more complex structure of the VSF, the following materials were assigned, as illustrated
 53 in Fig. S-7:

- 54 • Stainless steel lining (*Edelstahlverkleidung*)
- 55 • Air (*Luft*; for OpenFOAM only)
- 56 • Lean concrete (*Magerbeton*)
- 57 • Reinforced concrete (*Stahlbeton*)
- 58 • Sheet steel (*Stahlblech*)
- 59 • Substrate (*Substratum*)

Fig. S- 7. The materials assigned to the elements of the slot VSF, including stainless steel lining (*Edelstahlverkleidung*), lean concrete (*Magerbeton*), reinforced concrete (*Stahlbeton*), sheet steel (*Stahlblech*), and substrate (*Substratum*). The air (*Luft*) component was required for the OpenFOAM simulation only.

1.2 Add Camera for Rendering & Determine Resolution

To render the landscape of the VSF for Unreal Engine, a camera must be placed in the Blender model. To optimize camera recording, the following camera settings were used:

- *Type*: Orthographic
- *Orthographic Scale*: 48.000 (independent of image resolution)

In addition, the *Render Engine* was set to Eevee, and the *View Transform* parameter was set to Raw (cf., Fig. S-8).

The X-Y resolution is crucial, and it cannot be used as a default for other models. Both X and Y resolution depend on the import into Unreal Engine, where the landscape is composed of *Landscape Components*, which define the resolution of the scene (cf., Fig. S-9). The following settings were used for the VSF:

- *Resolution X*: 16 321 px
- *Resolution Y*: 4 081 px
- *File Format*: PNG
- *Color*: BW
- *Color Depth*: 16

The model bounding boxes, defined by the X-Y resolution, should be as tight as possible, which imposed an aspect ratio of approximately 4:1 in the case of the VSF. The X value of 16 321 px was determined by the landscape import options in Unreal Engine. Specifically, for high-resolution rendering of videos, the target value of the longest model axis (i.e., the *x*-axis) was "at least 4K pixels". Accounting for the best possible resolution in Unreal Engine with 255×255 quads (*Section Size*), the smallest *Number of Components* that enabled the desired *Overall Resolution* (in X-direction), was 16, yielding 4081 px. 15 X-components were not suitable because it led to an overall X-resolution of 3821 px only. Note that Unreal Engine only accepts integer values for *Number of Components*, and automatically calculates the *Overall Resolution* in X and Y-directions, based on the number of quads (i.e., *Section Size*) and *Number of Components*.

After defining the X-resolution, the resolution in Y-direction for the Blender model was found by testing for the tightest bounding box dimensions that still entirely encompassed the VSF. This bounding box size was relevant for performance improvement of the simulation, and achieved with 64 X-components and 16 Y-components in Unreal Engine, leading to an overall Y-resolution of 4081 px. Notably, irrelevant empty space should be avoided, as it still causes computational load. More details on the landscape import settings in Unreal Engine can be found in subsection 2.3 (Fig. S-9).

Fig. S- 8. Blender camera settings. Dotted green boxes surround modified defaults.

Fig. S- 9. Scene settings in Blender to optimize the camera canvas and resolution. Dotted green boxes surround modified defaults.

1.3 Elevation Mapping (Heightmap / Topography)

To add elevation (height) information, a grayscale heightmap was generated, ranging from the maximum model height (white) to the model bottom (black). For gray-scaling, a new material was created, representing the model height. With the VSF model selected, the material was created from the *Shading* menu in Blender (Fig. S-10) by modifying materials (i.e., textures defined in *Scene Collection*) of the VSF.

Fig. S-10. The Shading menu in the Blender interface (top green box).

The materials (e.g., *Height_Substratum*) were activated as shown in Fig. S-11 (top-center green box). Next, the purple code boxes framed in Fig. S-11 (bottom-center green boxes) were added. These two code boxes contain the minimum (*zmin*) and maximum (*zmax*) height values of the **entire** model. If those are unknown, the model height minimum and maximum can be inferred from a CAD model, that is, from the *z*-axis of the largest mesh. In the case of the slot VSF, the largest mesh was a combination of the reinforced concrete (*Stahlbeton*) and stainless steel lining (*Edelstahlverkleidung*) elements. *zmin* was defined by the reinforced concrete element (0.12 m), and *zmax* by the stainless steel lining element (3.31 m). These *zmin* and *zmax* included an added and subtracted 0.02 m above the bottom of the model and below the top of the model, respectively. That is, the defined *zmin* was 0.02 m higher, and *zmax* was 0.02 m lower than the model bottom and top, respectively. Otherwise, errors may occur during import in Unreal Engine due to insufficient tolerance. The heightmaps were applied to elements consisting of the following materials:

- *Height_Edelstahlverkleidung* (stainless steel lining)

- 114 • Height_Magerbeton_ref (lean concrete)
- 115 • Height_Stahlbeton (reinforced concrete)
- 116 • Height_Substratum (substrate)

Fig. S- 11. The Height_Substratum control (top green box) showing the functional link map zmin Substratum and zmax Substratum settings (center-bottom green box).

117 With the camera positioned over the model (cf., subsection 1.2), the grayscale image was
 118 rendered by pressing the F12 key, and saved in PNG format.

119 1.4 Additional Tips for DEM Integration

120 To import a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) into Blender the DEM needs to be converted into
 121 a format that Blender can understand and manipulate. DEM files often come in formats such
 122 as GeoTIFF, which contain spatial elevation data, but the GeoTIFF format is not supported by
 123 Blender by default. To circumvent this limitation, either use a geospatial add-on, or convert
 124 a GeoTIFF file to a grayscale heightmap (PNG or TIFF format) using GIS desktop software
 125 like QGIS (QGIS Development Team 2022). In a grayscale heightmap, DEM elevations are
 126 converted to gray intensity values where the brightness of each pixel represents elevation. In
 127 Blender, a georeferenced grayscale heightmap can be handled using a *Displace* modifier to create
 128 the terrain mesh with the following workflow:

- 129 1. Open Blender and delete the default cube.
- 130 2. Add a Plane: *Add > Mesh > Plane*. This plane is the base for the terrain.
- 131 3. Subdivide the Plane: Enter *Edit* mode (e.g., with the Tab key), right-click the plane, and
 132 choose *Subdivide*. In the *Subdivide* tool options, increase the number of subdivisions to
 133 create more geometry details for the terrain. A higher number of subdivisions results in
 134 more detailed terrain but requires more computational resources. Exit *Edit* mode (Tab
 135 key).
- 136 4. Add a *Displace* modifier:

- 137 • Go to the *Modifiers* tab (screw wrench icon) in the *Properties* panel.
- 138 • Click on *Add Modifier* and select *Displace*.
- 139 • In the *Displace* modifier settings, find the *Texture* frame, and click *New* to create a
- 140 new texture.
- 141 5. Configure the *Texture*:
- 142 • Go to the *Texture* tab (chess pattern icon) in the *Properties* panel.
- 143 • Choose the above-created texture from the dropdown menu.
- 144 • Under *Type*, select *Image or Movie*, and open the heightmap (PNG or TIFF) image
- 145 created with GIS software.
- 146 • Consider to adjust the *Strength* of the displacement in the modifier settings to get a
- 147 correct elevation scale.
- 148 6. Apply the displacement: Once the terrain appearance is satisfactory, apply the *Displace*
- 149 modifier to make the changes permanent.

150 Further improvement of a DEM can be achieved by applying specific materials and textures

151 in Blender, corresponding to surface properties, such as a cobble riverbed or vegetated alluvial

152 plane. There are also GIS Add-ons for Blender to import geospatial data directly into Blender.

2 UNREAL ENGINE

2.1 Hardware Settings

For the simulation performance, the graphics card with its graphics processing unit (GPU) was critical. Three computers were used for the simulations, but only the one with an AMD Radeon TUF-RX 7900 XTX (24 GB Video RAM) was able to render a voxel edge length of 0.024 m.

🔔 Note: Working with Unreal Engine

To get started with Unreal Engine, the developer documentation provides extensive guidance, including tutorials at <https://dev.epicgames.com/documentation/en-us/unreal-engine/understanding-the-basics-of-unreal-engine>. The following sections provide detailed information on the Unreal Engine workflow used in this study. Familiarizing with Unreal Engine is advisable before implementing this workflow.

2.2 Unreal Engine User Interface and Hardware Settings

This study used Unreal Engine 5.4 (Epic Games 2024b), and later 5.6. The virtual world was created using the *Third Person* template, which creates a virtual world with a controllable character in a camera view that is advantageous for observing simulations. The graphical user interface of Unreal Engine with the activated *Third Person* template is shown in Fig. S-12, highlighting the following controls:

1. **Project** menu bar: Open projects and levels, manage plugins, and change project settings.
2. **Editor Viewport**: Interactive representation of the virtual world to adjust objects and their levels.
3. **Content Browser**: View project files, including folder management.
4. **Outliner**: Display all objects/bodies of the current level, which can be moved to different folders.
5. **Level** menu bar: Switch between up to eight levels in the *Editor Viewport*; here, mostly *Selection Mode* and *Modeling Mode* were used.
6. **Details**: Show details of currently selected objects.

2.3 Import Blender Landscape

2.3.1 Resolution parameters

This section describes the resolution parameters mentioned in the Blender section on the model extents (subsection 2.3). Notably, the landscape resolution is defined by four parameters, and it also depends on the camera resolution defined in Blender (see Blender camera resolution Fig. S-9):

- **Heightmap Resolution**: The heightmap resolution was defined with the Blender model (see subsection 1.2).

Fig. S- 12. The graphical user interface of Unreal Engine with the *Third Person* template activated, and indication of the (1) Project menu bar, (2) Editor Viewport, (3) Content Browser, (4) Outliner, (5) Level menu, and (6) Details (of highlighted elements/objects).

- 182 • **Overall Resolution:** 16 321 × 4 081 pixel for offline rendering; 4 081 × 766 pixel for
183 runtime (gameply) rendering.
- 184 • **Section Size:** Determine in units of *Quads*, this value was set to 255x255, leading to
185 the highest possible resolution of the landscape in the virtual world with 255 quads per
186 section.
- 187 • **Sections Per Component:** Internal size of the components, for example, 1×1 or 2×2.
188 Where 2×2 leads to a worse resolution than 1×1 because only half of the components are
189 available. Thus, 1×1 was selected.
- 190 • **Number of Components:** The total number of components for the landscape determined
191 the resolution of the image in Blender (see subsection 1.2). The maximum resolution of
192 65281×65281 pixels can be achieved with 32x32 components, but this would cause a too
193 big landscape, making the simulation crash. Since high resolution was still required for
194 offline rendering, the number of components was adjusted until the X-value was above
195 this value.
196 For offline rendering, this was achieved with 64 X-components and 16 Y-components,
197 based on the narrowest possible bounding box to keep the non-relevant model area as
198 small as possible. Thus, the total number of components for offline rendering was 1024.
199 For runtime rendering, this was achieved with 16 X-components and 3 Y-components.
200 Thus, the total number of components for runtime rendering was 48.

201 2.3.2 Import of the Landscape (Heightmap)

202 The landscape created with Blender (see subsection 1.3) is imported in the same space where
203 the resolution settings were made by clicking on *Import from File*.

204 More guidance on the implementation of a landscape in Unreal Engine can be found in
205 the developer docs at [https://dev.epicgames.com/documentation/en-us/unreal-engine/landscape-](https://dev.epicgames.com/documentation/en-us/unreal-engine/landscape-technical-guide-in-unreal-engine)
206 [technical-guide-in-unreal-engine](https://dev.epicgames.com/documentation/en-us/unreal-engine/landscape-technical-guide-in-unreal-engine).

207 **2.4 Distance Fields: Representation of Objects for Particle Interactions**

208 The precision of a model is driven by distance fields. The following paragraphs introduce the
209 concept of distance fields and their optimization for the precise yet efficient representation of
210 objects in Unreal Engine.

211 **2.4.1 Signed Distance Fields (SDFs) and Mesh Distance Fields (MDFs)**

212 Signed distance fields (SDFs) and mesh distance fields (MDFs) are concepts used in computer
213 graphics and game development to quantify the position of objects relative to each other.

214 An SDF is a volumetric data structure. Each point in the volume holds the shortest distance
215 to a surface. The sign convention for the distance is positive if the point is outside the surface
216 and negative if it is inside. This convention aids in determining the position of a point relative
217 to the surface. SDFs are used in Unreal Engine for efficient and smooth operations on complex
218 geometries, such as effects like collision detection, ray marching, or ambient occlusion. In the
219 context of the Niagara Fluids plugin, SDFs also aid in defining boundaries of solids (i.e., flow
220 obstacles) in a fluid simulation, allowing the fluid to flow around or interact with solid objects.
221 To optimize computing efficiency, PIC-FLIP simulations in Niagara Fluids use pre-computed
222 distance fields, enabling quick assessment and responses to particle-object interactions.

223 An MDF is a variation of a distance field for mesh objects. It stores the distance from
224 each point in the volume to the nearest surface of a (solid boundary) mesh. In Unreal Engine,
225 MDFs are used for rendering and simulation purposes such as shadows, illumination, and
226 ambient occlusion. Thus, they are useful for dynamic lighting effects as they provide detailed
227 information about the geometry of the scene. In the context of the Niagara Fluid plugin, MDFs
228 help to represent the interaction between fluids and complex mesh geometries, such as fluid
229 flows around dynamic (actors like fish) or static (e.g., walls) mesh objects.

230 In the simulation of fluids, MDFs also play a critical role in collision handling and the
231 updating of particle properties. For instance, MDFs enable the simulation to determine how
232 close each fluid particle is to objects in the scene. When a particle comes near an object, its
233 properties like velocity and position can be adjusted using MDFs to reflect the interaction with
234 the surface of the object. Specifically, an MDF serves to calculate the normal at the point of the
235 nearest approach, which in turn can be used to modify the particle velocity, simulate a bounce, or
236 slide along the surface. Also, when particle properties are transferred to the grid, the influence
237 of MDFs on these properties is incorporated. Thus, the grid-based representation of the fluid
238 takes into account the interactions between particles and objects, leading to more realistic fluid
239 behavior around objects.

240 **2.4.2 Object geometry and MDF optimization**

241 The precise representation of imported Blender objects requires adjustments to the MDF. By
242 activating the *MDF-view* in Unreal Engine, the MDFs of all objects are displayed in grayscale.
243 This MDF representation of the object surfaces is what particles "experience" as solid boundaries
244 determining collisions of fluid particles with the model. However, despite diligent preparation,
245 the MDF may appear inadequate in many areas. When models have complex geometries with

246 sharp angles, or when they have a large spatial extent in the order of multiple tens of meters in
247 one direction, the MDF resolution in Unreal Engine is poor.

248 The poor representation is the result of the MDF resolution in Unreal Engine, which is
249 limited to 128×128×128 pixel units (in X, Y, and Z directions), dividing the geometry into
250 128 smoothed pixels along the longest axis of the imported object. The 128-pixel resolution
251 cannot be modified. Still, there are ways to refine the MDF, such as breaking a model into
252 smaller elements.

253 In Unreal Engine, MDFs are controlled through *Project Settings > Software Ray Tracing*. A
254 *Distance Field Voxel Density* serves for converting the standard mesh scale into distance field
255 voxel dimensions. Increasing this value triggers a rebuild of the MDFs, resulting in improved
256 resolution and high memory consumption. Additionally, in the properties of the *Static Mesh*,
257 the *Distance Field Resolution Scale* needs to be 1.0 to avoid solid objects being permeable.

3 NIAGARA FLUIDS

3.1 About the Niagara System

3.1.1 Activation and initialization of the plugin

Niagara Fluids shipped as a plugin with Unreal Engine 5.0 (April 2022) and has since seen substantial updates. Most notably the introduction of heterogeneous volumes as an experimental path in Unreal Engine 5.2 and Sparse Volume Texture (SVT) caching/import improvements in Unreal Engine 5.3. In Unreal Engine 5.4, Niagara Fluids gained several solver and workflow upgrades, most notably improved 2d-liquid surfacing, a pressure solver for 2d gas, higher-precision boundary conditions for 3d fluids, two-way coupling between 3D liquids and GPU particles, and caching support for 2d gas. In Unreal Engine 5.6, Epic added river-spline integration for shallow-water via a new *Shallow Water River* actor that builds a Niagara 2d fluid simulation from *Water Body River* splines, and introduced stability/performance tweaks (e.g., resetting Niagara systems that traverse too many mesh tiles to avoid precision issues) alongside broader engine-level performance gains.

To enable the Niagara Fluids plugin in Unreal Engine, click through *Edit > Plugins > FX*, check *Niagara* and *NiagaraFluids*, and restart Unreal Engine.

To create a simulation, a new *Niagara System* was established in the *Content Drawer* on the bottom left of the Unreal Editor interface, where the following actions were taken:

- Click on the + *Add* button, selected *FX > Niagara System > New system from a template or behavior example* from the context menu.
- Choose a template that best suits the case; alternatively, a blank system can be created:
 - This study used the *Grid 3D FLIP Hose* template, which includes a particle emitter.
 - If a blank system is used, a *Niagara Emitter* would be needed to be added with a right-click in the emitters panel (*Add Emitter*).

These actions add a *New Niagara System* to the *All > Content* folder in the *Content Drawer* (i.e., *Content Browser*). To work with it, grab the *NewNiagara System* with the mouse and pull it into the active level, that is, the Unreal Engine Viewport (Editor).

3.1.2 User interface

The user interface of the Niagara System contains important elements for setting up and controlling fluid simulations. The following descriptions refer to these elements, highlighted in Fig. S-13:

1. **Menu Bar:** Multiple kinds of data processing and project handling actions.
2. **Tools:** Essential utilities, such as the *Compile* function for implementing effects.
3. **Preview:** Visualize the currently active effect, displaying it as it appears in the virtual environment.
4. **User Parameters:** Set up real-time links using an *ActorBlueprint*.
5. **System Overview:** Stages and modules of an effect. For instance, the *Emitter Update* stage and the *Spawn Rate* module can be found here. The order of the modules within the stages is crucial for the playback of effects.

- 297 6. **Scratch Pad**: Implemented custom modules.
- 298 7. **Selection**: Modifying the parameters of effect modules.
- 299 8. **Curves**: Create and edit curve properties, such as color curves (here: for particle velocity
- 300 coloring).
- 301 9. **Niagara Log**: Records any errors encountered.
- 302 10. **Timeline**: Adjust the runtime duration of an effect.

Fig. S- 13. The User Interface of the Niagara System plugin, highlighting the locations of the (1) Menu bar, (2) Tools, (3) Preview, (4) Parameters, (5) System Overview, (6) Scratch Pad, (7) Curves, (8) Niagara Log, and (10) Timeline.

303 3.1.3 Relevant Codes in the Niagara System

304 Regarding the technical implementation of the PIC-FLIP method, the official Unreal Engine

305 documentation (Epic Games 2024a) provided little information. More detailed information was

306 inferred from the source code of the Niagara System, even though the C++ source files had

307 little to no inline comments explaining the workflow. To gain a comprehensive understanding

308 of the implementation of the PIC-FLIP method in Niagara Fluids, Kim 2017 and Englesson

309 et al. 2011 provide more descriptions. While Englesson et al. 2011 is a rather short method-

310 ological overview recommended by the developers (Penney 2024), Kim 2017 provides detailed

311 information on writing code for physics-based fluid animation with hybrid particle-grid solvers,

312 including mathematical background. In Unreal Engine, traces of similar implementations can

313 be found in the following source code (located in UnrealEngine/Engine/Plugins/FX/Ni-

314 agara/Source/):

- 315 • Niagara/Public/NiagaraSystemSimulation.h
- 316 • Niagara/Private/Experimental/NiagaraMeshUvMapping.h

- 317 • Niagara/Classes/NiagaraDataInterfaceMeshCommon.h
- 318 • Niagara/Classes/NiagaraSimCache.h

319 3.2 Rendering

320 3.2.1 Renderer types

321 The visual effects system (FX) in Unreal Engine enables multiple options for rendering fluids.
 322 For example, a mesh renderer for particle effects to 3d meshes, a beam renderer for light/laser-
 323 like effects, a volume renderer for realistic environmental effects, and more. In this study, the
 324 water and sprite renderers were used for different purposes.

325 The water renderer is designed for simulating and rendering realistic water surfaces, such
 326 as oceans, rivers, lakes, or the slot VSF. It has capabilities to handle the dynamic nature of
 327 water like waves, reflections, and interaction with environmental actors, such as wind and light.
 328 This renderer is ideal for realistic visualization of water bodies and scenarios where the visual
 329 properties of water are a priority. In addition to information from PIC-FLIP simulations, the
 330 *Water Renderer* uses advanced shader programming to achieve realistic results, which is more
 331 computationally demanding compared to the sprite renderer.

332 The sprite renderer is a general-purpose renderer in Niagara for rendering particles with
 333 computational efficiency. Rather than visualizing a compound water body, it depicts single
 334 particles (i.e., water blobs) in the simulation, including their attributes like size or color related
 335 to velocity.

336 To set up the simulation of the VSF, the water renderer was deactivated and the sprite
 337 renderer was activated, as the latter allowed for a more efficient and computationally less
 338 demanding representation of the fluid. Additionally, the `Grid3D_Flip_Secondary_Emitter`,
 339 which by default is active and simulates foam, was deactivated since its utility is primarily in
 340 conjunction with the water renderer (cf., Fig. S-14). The water renderer was reactivated later to
 341 enable a realistic representation of the water surface.

Fig. S- 14. Activation of the sprite renderer (left) and deactivation of the secondary emitter rendering (right), which serves to visualize foam.

3.2.2 High-resolution rendering (render-grid up-sampling)

In Niagara-FLIP the Render Grid Resolution Mult (κ_r) acts solely as a post-process up-sampling factor for the volumetric render grid: the effective march-step through the volume is $\Delta v_{l, \text{render}} = \Delta v_{l, \text{sim}} / \kappa_r$, where the simulation voxel size is $\Delta v_{l, \text{sim}} = L / \text{Num Cells Max Axis}$ set in the *Grid* section of the emitter summary. Thus, with a longitudinal model length of 48 m and $\text{Num Cells Max Axis} = 10^3$, keeping $\kappa_r = 1$ preserves the (wetted) cell width while leaving the Lagrangian particle kernel unchanged. The default value of $\kappa_r = 2$ merely halves Δr_{render} for shading, doubling the GPU memory footprint, but it does not halve the particle diameter nor influence the FLIP timestep. Because Unreal enforces a hard cap of $\text{Num Cells Max Axis} \leq 10^3$ per fluid volume, setting $\kappa_r > 1$ prevented any further mesh refinement along the VSF. Consequently, $\kappa_r = 1$ was retained to maximize spatial resolution within the 10^3 -cell limit. Moreover, optical sharpening, if required, could be obtained with the lower-cost Render Step Size Mult parameter.

3.2.3 Color-coding of particles

To visualize the flow velocity of the particles, a *Color* module was created in the *Particle Update* stage (cf., Fig. S-15). The color coding reflected the real, physical velocity of the particles (in cm s^{-1}), which was crucial for the analysis of flow behavior. For color coding, the *Color Option* was linked with the dynamic input *Scale Linear Color by Curve*. A color scale was then configured and mapped to the particle velocity. This involved creating curve points in the *Curves* menu by holding down the mouse wheel to assign X-Y coordinates. Here, the x -axis corresponded to the particle velocity in cm s^{-1} and the y -axis to the color intensity, ranging from 0 to 1. This process was applied to the three color curves – red, green, and blue (RGB) – so that the color coding corresponded to the OpenFOAM output. Specifically, the color gradient scaling in Niagara Fluids matched the OpenFOAM exports with ParaView, and scaled flow velocity coloring from 0.0 m s^{-1} (blue) to 2.0 m s^{-1} (red). The *Alpha* color curve for transparency was not used in this study.

Fig. S-15. Elements and structure of the Color module.

To associate the x -axis with the absolute velocity of the particles, the *CurveIndex* parameter was linked to the vector length of the *Particle Velocity*. To enable accurate color representation, the material of the particles was modified in the *Sprite Renderer*. As all simulations of the *3D Liquid* were based on the *Debug3DFLIP* material, a copy of this active material was

372 created. This was accomplished by clicking on the magnifying glass icon to highlight the
 373 material in the *Content Browser*. Then, the material was copied into a new folder and renamed
 374 *ParticleVelocityColor*.

Fig. S- 16. Detailed view of the Sprite renderer for linking the color index to particle velocity along the x -axis.

375 In the copied material, the color blue was replaced with white by creating a new *VectorParam*.
 376 This parameter was multiplied by the *Particle Color* and designated as the *Base Color* (Fig. S-
 377 17). The new material was saved and selected in the *Sprite Renderer*. In particular, the *Base*
 378 *Color* and *Emissive Color* were adjusted so that the color values were transferred directly from
 379 the *Particle Color* to the sprites without blue shading.

380 The new material was assigned to the sprite renderer, as shown in Fig. S-18

381 3.3 Fluid Parameters and their Implementation

382 3.3.1 User parameters (global)

383 In the *Content Browser*, the Niagara asset was opened by double-clicking on it (alternatively,
 384 highlighting the actor in the *Outliner* was used), which opened the PIC-FLIP simulation *System*
 385 *Overview*. The Unreal PIC-FLIP system of the VSF can be found by navigating in the *Content*
 386 *Browser* to *All > Content > FluidSimulation > double-click on FluidSim*. In the bottom-
 387 left of the *Final-Simulation (System Overview map)* window, the *User Parameters* tab enables
 388 modifications of critical parameters for the simulation. For simulating water flowing through
 389 the VSF, the following *User Parameters* were modified:

- 390 • **World Grid Extents:** Define the limits of the simulation in its spatial extent in the virtual
 391 world. Any particles outside this area were not simulated and deleted. For the simulation
 392 of the VSF, this parameter was set to 4800 600 400 (X, Y, Z).
- 393 • **Collision Velocity Mult:** Set collision interactions; must be larger than zero to simulate
 394 any impulses. For instance, consider a scenario in which water is poured out of a glass.
 395 If this parameter was set to 0, it would be impossible to shake the water out of the glass;
 396 it would only flow driven by gravity. Thus, for the simulation of the VSF, this parameter
 397 was set to 1.0.

Fig. S- 17. Function map in Unreal Editor, showing the new copied material called ParticleVelocityColor for coloring sprites with a velocity scale from 0 m s^{-1} (blue) to 2 m s^{-1} (red).

Fig. S- 18. Activation of the new ParticleVelocityColor in the Sprite Renderer.

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- **Num Cells Max Axis:** Determine the cell size in the simulation by configuring the number of cells for the longest axis of the simulation domain (here: the x -axis). This parameter affects the particle size, calculated as the quotient of *World Grid Extents Max Axis* / *Num Cells Max Axis*. For the simulation of the VSF, this parameter was set to 2000.
- **Particles Per Cell:** Set the number of particles per cell. The default value of 8 was used here.
- **SpawnRate:** Property of the particle emitter; determines the quantity of fluid particles emitted into the Niagara system per second. Its default of 20,000 particles per second was changed for the simulation of flow scenarios with different discharges. See details in Sec. 3.7.1.
- **Show Bounds:** View the bounding box of the simulation with red lines, defined by *World Grid Extents*.

- **Water Height:** Set the water level (Z-coordinate) at the beginning of the simulation, which was 0.0 for the VSF simulation.

3.3.2 Emitter parameters

In the *System Overview* map, also the emitter properties can be controlled. To this end, click on the *Emitter* control box on the map, and *Emitter Summary*. In the *Details* tab, a set of control parameters for the simulation becomes available, organized in *Sim*, *Collisions*, *Particle Spawn*, and *Render* groups. The **Sim parameters** are:

- **World Grid Extent:** See *User Parameters*.
- **Num Cells Max Axis:** See *User Parameters*.
- **Pressure Iterations:** See *User Parameters*.
- **Pressure Relaxation:** Affects the apparent fluid viscosity.
- **PIC FLIP Ratio:** Balance between the PIC and FLIP methods during the simulation (see Discussion in the main manuscript).
- **Use Rasterization:** Boolean choice to enable a rasterization grid for velocity (True in the case of the VSF).
- **Show Bounds:** See *User Parameters*.

In addition, the frequency at which particles are generated or emitted in a Niagara System is defined by the **Spawn Rate** (see *User Parameters* and Sec. 3.7.1).

3.3.2.1 Resolution Multiplier

In Niagara Fluids, mesh (grid) resolution is configured in the *Grid 3D Set Resolution* module, which is typically placed in the *Emitter Spawn* stage so that the mesh sizes are established before simulation stages run. The base cell size is computed from the world-space bounds and the target number of cells along the longest axis. Several Niagara Fluids templates expose per-mesh resolution scalars (**multipliers**) that set a mesh resolution relative to this base. For example, the lighting mesh uses a down-sample factor (default 2) applied to a pre-shading volume to determine a coarser lighting resolution. Setting this factor to 1 disables down-sampling (lighting mesh matches the base resolution); larger values reduce lighting-mesh resolution.

Accordingly, **Resolution Multiplier** change the mesh resolution of the targeted volume (e.g., lighting or render volumes), not the FLIP particle (blob) size directly. Particle size/spacing in the liquid solver primarily follows the simulation mesh scale and related parameters (such as the number of cells along the max axis and template-specific particle fill settings), and can also change when the world grid extents are altered. In this study, setting the multiplier to 1 is consistent with "no relative scaling" of the derived mesh (different from the default of 2).

444 3.3.2.2 World Scale

445

446 The *WorldScale* is located in the *Emitter Update* stage in the *Grid 3D Update Sim Attributes*
 447 module. *WorldScale* functions as a multiplier that permits the alteration of particle size related
 448 to the constant (invariable preset) cell size. Here, the default *WorldScale* of 1.0 1.0 1.0 was
 449 used.

450 3.3.2.3 Pressure Addon

451

452 Within Niagara Fluids, the pressure projection on the mesh works as follows: after advection
 453 and forcing, a Poisson equation for pressure is solved iteratively and the velocity is corrected by
 454 subtracting the pressure gradient. In Epic Games's templates, these steps are exposed through
 455 simulation stages with user-adjustable parameters such as *Pressure Relaxation* and *Pressure*
 456 *Solve Iterations*.

457 The *PressureAddon*, implemented as a per-parcel High-Level Shader Language (HLSL)
 458 module, injected an auxiliary scalar that counteracted spurious parcel divergence during the
 459 pressure projection stage. This module served as a purely empirical tuning parameter and it
 460 is unrelated to ambient static pressure. This was necessary because Niagara's FLIP pressure
 461 projection lets parcels compress along densely packed flowpaths at sharp edges (e.g., through
 462 slots). Thus, residual stresses let parcels overlap (i.e., "lock") and affect the computed mass flux.
 463 Therefore, at each timestep, the *PressureAddon* writes a small extra term into the pressure
 464 map. This offset pushed interpenetrating parcels apart, and prevented parcel locking.

465 The *PressureAddon* was added inside the module *Grid3D_PressureIteration*
 466 (*Solve Pressure* stage), mapping it to a user parameter for interactive editing. Conceptually,
 467 the modification `Pressure += PressureAddon;` applies a uniform offset to the mesh pressure
 468 after each Jacobi update (see Fig. S-19):

$$\nabla^2 p = \mathcal{R}(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}), \quad \mathbf{u}^{n+1} = \mathbf{u}^n - \frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p, \quad (1)$$

469 Thus, replacing p by $p + C$ leaves the velocity correction unchanged because $\nabla(p + C) = \nabla p$.

```

if (FluidCellCount > 0)
{
    float JacobiPressure = (P_right + P_left + P_up + P_down + P_front + P_back - dx * dx * Divergence / dt + BoundaryAdd) / FluidCellCount;
    Pressure = (1.f - Weight) * P_center + Weight * JacobiPressure;
    Pressure += 400; //Change PressureAddon value here!!!
}
#endif

```

Fig. S- 19. Implementation of the *PressureAddon* in the *JacobiPressure* update.

470 3.3.3 Particle-landscape collisions

471 To enable collisions between particles and the landscape, that is, the VSF, it was defined as the
 472 source landscape for collisions in the Niagara System (*LandscapeCollisions*).

473 3.3.4 Stable fluids method

474 The *stable fluid* method, introduced by [Stam 1999](#), is an advancement milestone in compu-
 475 tational fluid dynamics, particularly for real-time applications like computer graphics. Stam's

476 method offers an efficient, stable approach to simulating fluid flow on a mesh, balancing the com-
477 putational demands with the need for physical realism. Its influence extends beyond hydraulic
478 engineering into the realms of computer graphics and animation, demonstrating versatility and
479 robustness in various applications of fluid dynamics.

480 Traditional explicit numerical methods for solving the Navier-Stokes equations can be un-
481 stable, especially for large time steps or high Reynolds numbers. This instability can lead to
482 numerical artifacts, like exploding velocities or loss of mass conservation, which are unaccept-
483 able in both engineering simulations and visual effects. The *stable fluid* method addresses these
484 stability issues by using a semi-implicit approach for the advection and diffusion terms in the
485 Navier-Stokes equations. This approach allows for larger time steps without sacrificing stability.
486 The key idea is to separate the advection (i.e., movement of fluid particles) from other forces,
487 such as pressure and viscosity.

488 To maintain incompressibility, that is, constant density, in the fluid, the *stable fluid* method
489 uses a projection step. After updating the velocities using the semi-implicit method, a Poisson
490 equation for the pressure is solved. The resulting pressure field is then used to project the
491 velocity field onto the space of divergence-free fields, ensuring incompressibility. This method
492 is particularly able to produce realistic simulations of fluid-like behavior (smoke, water, or air
493 movement) efficiently. It is well-suited for real-time applications like computer graphics, where
494 computational resources are limited, and high frame rates are required.

495 While the *stable fluid* method represents a powerful and stable computation scheme, it does
496 have limitations, for example, in handling complex boundary conditions and simulating highly
497 turbulent flows accurately. For instance, small-scale vortices and detailed turbulent structures
498 cannot be captured without substantially increasing the mesh resolution. Also, the semi-implicit
499 treatment of advection can introduce numerical diffusion, leading to smoothing effects affecting
500 the simulation of sharp interfaces or highly dynamic interactions within the fluid. To this
501 end, various extensions and improvements have been proposed to enhance its applicability and
502 accuracy. Issues regarding the handling of complex interfaces and complex boundaries were
503 addressed by a *ghost fluid* method (Fedkiw & Liu 2001), and numerical diffusion can be treated
504 by higher mesh resolution.

505 3.4 Numerical Schemes in PIC-FLIP.

506 The Niagara Fluids solver implements the PIC-FLIP algorithm using an operator-splitting
507 scheme that separates each timestep into force accumulation, advection, diffusion, and pres-
508 sure projection (Stam 1999, Brackbill et al. 1988, Bridson 2008). Advection is handled by
509 Lagrangian parcel transport: parcel positions are integrated forward through the velocity field
510 using forward Euler time integration, which is first-order accurate in time. Parcel-mesh and
511 mesh-parcel transfers are based on trilinear (cloud-in-cell) interpolation, yielding first-order
512 spatial accuracy in the transfer step (Zhu & Bridson 2005, Brackbill & Ruppel 1986). Diffusion
513 is treated implicitly with a backward Euler scheme, also first-order accurate in time. Pressure
514 projection solves the Poisson equation $\nabla^2 p = (\rho \Delta t)^{-1} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}^*$ on the Eulerian mesh using an
515 iterative solver, where the number of iterations per timestep is controlled by the `Pressure`
516 `Iterations` parameter in Niagara Fluids. Velocity components are stored at face centers and
517 pressure at cell centers in a staggered marker-and-cell (MAC) arrangement (Harlow & Welch
518 1965). The overall time-stepping scheme is first-order accurate owing to the operator-splitting
519 formulation (Stam 1999). Please note that Niagara Fluids is a GPU-executed solver whose
520 source code is accessible under the Unreal Engine End User License Agreement via GitHub,

521 but is not documented at the level customary for scientific uses. The scheme descriptions above
 522 are therefore based on the published PIC-FLIP algorithm (Brackbill et al. 1988, Zhu & Bridson
 523 2005, Bridson 2008) that Niagara Fluids is documented to implement (Epic Games 2024a).

524 The computational domain consists of uniform cubic voxels with an edge length of $v_l = 0.024$ m
 525 (see main paper). No local mesh refinement or grading is available in Niagara Fluids; thus, all
 526 cells in the simulation container are identical. This uniform discretization contrasts with the
 527 variable-resolution mesh used in OpenFOAM (0.02–0.20 m). Because PIC-FLIP does not em-
 528 ploy adaptive mesh refinement, resolution tradeoffs are global: smaller voxels improve accuracy
 529 everywhere but increase memory consumption and computing time proportionally to v_l^{-3} .

530 Because PIC-FLIP advection is Lagrangian and unconditionally stable (Stam 1999), the
 531 Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) condition is not a stability constraint. However, the Courant
 532 number Co affects temporal accuracy because larger Co increases interpolation error during
 533 parcel–mesh transfers and widens the semi-Lagrangian backtrace distance. We estimated Co
 534 from the logged parcel velocities and the effective per-substep timestep as:

$$Co = \frac{u_{\max} \Delta t_{\text{sub}}}{v_l} \quad (2)$$

535 where u_{\max} is the maximum parcel velocity magnitude at a given cross section, $\Delta t_{\text{sub}} =$
 536 $1/(\text{Sequence Display Rate} \times K)$ is the substep duration, and K is the number of tempo-
 537 ral sub-samples per frame. For instance, for the HQ_{100} scenario with Sequence Display
 538 Rate = 120 fps and $K = 2$ temporal sub-samples, $\Delta t_{\text{sub}} = 1/(120 \times 2) \approx 0.0042$ s. With a
 539 maximum velocity of approximately 1.8 m s^{-1} (the design swimming speed) and $v_l = 0.024$ m,
 540 this yields $Co \approx 1.8 \times 0.0042 / 0.024 \approx 0.31$. For the lower discharges Q_{30} and Q_{\emptyset} , where
 541 Sequence Display Rate = 240 fps and maximum velocities were lower, Co remained below
 542 approximately 0.2. These values indicate that parcels displaced by less than one voxel per
 543 substep, which is favorable for the accuracy of the trilinear interpolation kernel used in the
 544 parcel–mesh transfers.

545 3.5 Particle Displacement (Teleport)

546 A custom Niagara HLSL-based module script was implemented to resolve instances in which
 547 FLIP particles numerically penetrate the static Landscape. For each particle with world position
 548 $\mathbf{p} = (x, y, z)$, the terrain height $z_L(x, y)$ and the terrain unit normal $\mathbf{n}(x, y)$ were sampled using
 549 `Get Height` and `Get World Normal`. If the vertical coordinate is strictly below the surface
 550 (i.e., $z < z_L(x, y)$; a strict $>$ test was used rather than \geq to avoid resting exactly on the surface),
 551 the position was incremented by a small step along the local surface normal:

$$\mathbf{p} \leftarrow \mathbf{p} + \Delta \zeta \mathbf{n}(x, y) \quad (3)$$

552 and the test was repeated until $z > z_L(x, y)$ was satisfied. The displacement was applied
 553 component-wise to X, Y, and Z (via `Break/Make Vector` and additive `Map Set` operations),
 554 which prevented particles from ratcheting up vertical faces or becoming trapped in gravity-driven
 555 oscillations that would occur with a pure $+Z$ correction. A step factor $\Delta \zeta$ was exposed as a
 556 dimensionless parameter (default 0.01 in this implementation). In Unreal Engine, 1 world unit
 557 equals 1 cm, so $\Delta \zeta$ should be chosen small relative to the flow and grid scales. Excessively
 558 large steps (on the order of centimeters) impart a zero-momentum *teleport* that behaves like a
 559 very rough, no-slip boundary and can artificially damp the resolved flow. This normal-directed,

560 strictly-above correction therefore provided a stable, low-bias way to push particles back out of
 561 the terrain while minimizing spurious artifacts of stuck particles.

Fig. S- 20. Node graph of the custom Teleport Particle Niagara module. The module samples the Landscape height $z_L(x, y)$ and unit normal $\mathbf{n}(x, y)$ at each particle position $\mathbf{p} = (x, y, z)$. If a particle is found below the terrain ($z < z_L$), its position is displaced by a small corrective step $\Delta \zeta \mathbf{n}$, applied component-wise to X , Y , and Z , to move it back above the surface. In the configuration shown, the step factor was set to $\Delta \zeta = 0.01$ (Unreal world units; 1 uu = 1 cm).

562 3.6 Parameter Links for Simulation Gameplay

563 The physical accuracy of the simulation in Unreal Engine is affected by pressure conditions,
 564 particle properties (spawn rate, size, and lifespan), and collision parameters. Pressure conditions
 565 control how water pressure builds up and how the water flows in response to obstacles and forces.
 566 The particle size and lifespan affect the overall representation (rendering, and therefore, flow
 567 rates) and behavior of the fluid. Here, an infinite particle lifespan was used because particles were
 568 eliminated by the *KillBox*. The particle emission rate refers to the Niagara System parameter of
 569 *SpawnRate*, which controls how many particles are generated and affects the fluid density. The
 570 collision parameters define how water interacts with other objects in the environment, including
 571 buoyancy and the ability to wet surfaces.

572 For adaption, that is, definition of flow scenarios, these parameters were linked with *Actor-*
 573 *Blueprints* enabling user interaction during gameplay (i.e., here, the simulation). To modify
 574 module parameters of an effect during gameplay, they must be linked to the *User Parameters*. As
 575 illustrated in Fig. S-21 for the spawn rate, this involves creating a variable in the *User Parameters*
 576 (e.g., a *Float* variable) and linking it to the *User Parameters* by clicking on the arrow to the
 577 right of the module parameter (here, *SpawnRate*). The functional link was then indicated by the
 578 presence of a blue USER icon preceding the variable.

Fig. S- 21. Defining the SpawnRate as a USER parameter.

579 To adjust the spawn rate and other parameters during the simulation gameplay, that is, in
 580 real-time, an *Actor* was created. In this *Actor*, the *3D Liquid* was selected within the *Niagara*
 581 *System Asset*. To allow the Fish character to be controlled with the keyboard during a simulation,
 582 an *Event Dispatcher* was created.

583 The keyboard mapping has been established through *Key Events*, which can alter parameter
 584 values using the function *Set Niagara Variable by String (Variable)*. For this purpose, the variable
 585 name was entered as *User*. (Name of the Variable), for instance, *User .SpawnRate* for the
 586 spawn rate, associated with the 1 key.

587 3.7 Inlet & Outlet Definitions

588 3.7.1 Spawn Rate

589 To adjust the spawn rate during the simulation gameplay, the *Niagara System* for *3D Liquids*
 590 was fully expanded by clicking the arrow. Then, the *Emitter Update* stage was opened, and
 591 the *Spawn Rate* (here: 001) module was selected. In the *Details* panel, a floating-point value
 592 for the spawn rate can be entered, which is preset to 20,000 particles per second. For the
 593 VSF simulations, it was crucial to be able to modify this value in real-time, that is, during the
 594 course of the simulation (i.e., gameplay). These modifications were necessary to yield the target
 595 discharges for flow scenarios of 60 L s^{-1} , 135 L s^{-1} , and $1,000 \text{ L s}^{-1}$. To achieve the interactive
 596 modification of the spawn rate during simulations, a new float variable *Particle SpawnRate* was
 597 created in the *User Parameters* menu and linked to the floating-point value of the spawn rate
 598 (see Fig. S-22).

599 3.7.2 Outflow parameter definitions (KillBox)

600 The outflow condition of a *Niagara Fluid System* corresponds to the deletion of particles at a
 601 predetermined point in the simulation. This deletion was achieved by using an invisible *KillBox*,

Fig. S- 22. Adjustment and linking of the Spawn Rate.

602 where particles were removed from the simulation upon (MDF) contact with the surface of
 603 the *KillBox*. For good performance, the *KillBox* should be at least as wide and high as the
 604 dimensions of the outflow area, ensuring all particles at the outflow boundary are deleted. To
 605 create the *KillBox*, a new *Kill Particles in Volume* module was added to the *Particle Update*
 606 stage. This new module automatically generated an invisible box. For a flexible adaptation of
 607 the *KillBox* to the model, the two vectors *Box Size* and *Origin Offset* were linked to the *User*
 608 *Parameters* (see Fig. S-23).

Fig. S- 23. Set up of the outflow boundary condition in the form of a KillBox.

609 3.8 Output Pipelines for Run-Time Simulation

Note

610 The post-processing for model calibration in this study used offline rendering of image series
 (see Sec. 3.8.5) where numeric data was written to logfiles (Kemmler & Schwindt 2025a,b).

611 3.8.1 Control sections

612 The flow behavior of the particles was observed through color coding, which, however, was
 613 predominantly limited to particle movement at the water surface. To make the flow behavior
 614 visible across entire cross-sections, an invisible box was inserted at key positions and configured
 615 in terms of its width (covering the entire cross-section) and length (0.02 m) for all XSs. The
 616 positions of these control cross-sections corresponded to control sections in the OpenFOAM
 617 simulation.

618 The fluid cross-section measured highlighted particles within the invisible box. For this
 619 highlighting, a local module named *CrossSection* was created. Two input vectors were defined,
 620 namely, the location vector and the X-Y-Z dimensions of the box. Subsequently, the coordi-
 621 nates of the particles and the box were transformed into the global coordinate system. The
 622 *IsPointInsideBox* function determined whether a particle was inside the box, and accordingly
 623 particles were made visible through a Color Boolean. To activate this feature, the module was

624 incorporated into the *Particle Update* stage. The final coordinate values of the input vectors
 625 were iteratively determined and stored in the module.

626 3.8.2 Particle data communication with Blueprints

627 To identify physical relations between elements of the virtual world (i.e., *ActorBlueprints*) and
 628 particle simulations, velocity data of the particles were exported. This was achieved through
 629 a newly created module, *Export Particle Data to Blueprint*, in the *Particle Update* stage. The
 630 particle velocity was then passed to *Actors* using *Vector to Send*. Additionally, in the *User*
 631 *Parameters*, two new objects named *TransferData* and *FishCollision* were created and linked
 632 with the *Callback Handler Parameter* option. This made it possible to depict a fish whose
 633 swimming strength is – not – sufficient to swim against currents with a maximum velocity
 634 of 1.8 m s^{-1} . More details on the implementation of particle-fish interactions are described in
 635 Sec. 4.2.

Fig. S- 24. Configuration of the Export Data module for sending simulation output data to an Actor Blueprint like fish for offline (a) and runtime (b) rendering.

636 3.8.3 Particle velocity measurement box

637 For the assessment of particle velocity in the VSF, a mobile measurement box was established,
 638 which was moved along the measurement positions (i.e., flow cross-sections). The mobile box
 639 computed and displayed the average particle velocity over a defined time interval of 40 s.

640 To implement the box, a *Local* module, named *UseMeasurementBoxForData* was created.
 641 Similar to the above-described cross-section box, two input vectors determined the position
 642 vector and the X-Y-Z dimensions of the box. The coordinates of the particles and the box were
 643 then transformed into the global coordinate system. The *IsPointInsideBox* function served to
 644 determine whether a particle was inside the box. The outcome, alongside with the particle
 645 position, was conveyed through an output parameter (Fig. S-24).

Fig. S- 25. Functional map of the particle velocity measurement box.

646 For the export of the determined particle data to the *LevelBlueprint* for visualization (display
 647 of flow velocity and water depth statistics), the *Export Particle Data to Blueprint* module was
 648 created in the *ParticleUpdate* stage. This involved linking the *Condition to export data* option
 649 with the output Boolean of the *IsPointInsideBox* function and the *Vector To Send* option with the
 650 output vector. Subsequently, the *Transfer Data* object was established in the *User Parameters*
 651 and connected with the *Callback Handler Parameter* option, ensuring that the exported data were
 652 stored for transfer to the *ActorBlueprint*. Setting the *GPU Allocation Mode* to *Per Particle*
 653 ensured that there was no upper limit to the number of particles captured. This module was
 654 activated by placing it in the *ParticleUpdate* stage above the *ExportData* module, thus exporting
 655 the velocity data of all particles within the box (Fig. S-24a).

656 For displaying the data in the active *ActorBlueprint*, the *NiagaraCallBackHandler* interface
 657 was implemented into the *ActorBlueprint* via the *Class Settings*. This enabled the *Receive*
 658 *Particle Data* event, which was invoked with each data export. To calculate and display the
 659 average particle velocity, another function was developed, which received the determined particle
 660 data and processed it using a loop. This function calculated the average over all particles in each
 661 box within the time interval of 40 s. The calculated averages were then displayed in the upper
 662 left corner of the *Characters Viewport*. Such measurement boxes were installed at the four XSs
 663 indicated in the main manuscript.

664 The calculated statistics, notably, 40-s mean, from the measurement points (sequentially
 665 measured by the box moving through the simulation) were stored in arrays for subsequent

666 processing and display. This approach allowed for a comprehensive analysis of particle velocity
 667 variations during the simulations.

668 Ideally, the acquisition of measurements and the calculation of results at all measurement
 669 points occurred simultaneously. However, due to hardware limitations, this was not feasible.
 670 Even the simultaneous measurement at just two cross-sections for velocity measurement and
 671 mean calculation considerably affected the simulation. Consequently, the measurements and
 672 calculations at the cross-sections were conducted sequentially. To accomplish this, an *Event Tick*
 673 via *Tick Intervall* (40 s) to execute a loop function that captured particle data was used. This
 674 adjustment ensured the smooth running of the simulation while recording flow velocity data.

675 To position the measurement box, the coordinates were converted from *WorldLocation* to
 676 *SimulationLocation* (Fig. S-26b). This programming approach enabled the insertion of the
 677 measuring cross-sections and provided flexibility in their placement within the model.

Fig. S- 26. Node graph for the conversion of the measuring coordinates from *WorldLocation* to *SimulationLocation* and storage in an array.

678 3.8.4 Water depth gauging

679 For measuring water depths, gauges with a vertical scale marked at 0.02-m intervals were created.
 680 For each gauge, in *Modeling Mode*, a cube measuring $0.05 \times 0.05 \text{ m}^2$ with a height of 1.0 m was
 681 modeled. Thus, the surface of the cube was subdivided with a *Height* value of 100 and a *Width*
 682 value of 5 (for line thickness). Subsequently, every second cell was marked, a material (color)
 683 was chosen, and applied using the *Assign Material* function. For better visualization, text fields
 684 were additionally inserted every 0.1 m (vertically). To this end, a new actor with a *Static Mesh*
 685 component was created and linked to the gauge. The text fields were generated in the actor
 686 through *Components* and positioned on the scale using the mouse (Fig. S-27).

687 3.8.5 Movie Render Queue

688 The Unreal PIC-FLIP model was rendered offline to ensure the repeatability of the simulations.
 689 Specifically, real-time rendering performance varied with the used computer because of internal

Fig. S- 27. Creation of the water depth gauge in Unreal Engine.

690 stability criteria in Unreal Engine, which are related to the available computing resources. To
 691 this end, offline rendering was used, namely the Movie Render Queue (see Fig. S-28). Pictures
 692 were taken at a *Sequence Display Rate* of 120 fps, but images were saved to disk only every
 693 240 fps. Offline rendering with Movie Render Queue is described in detail in Sec. 3.10.

694 In addition to the particle data written to the logfiles, output images were used to directly
 695 visualize flow patterns via coloring for the given discharge (SpawnRate) scenario.

696 3.9 Particle Properties & Logfiles

697 To quantify discharge and local kinematics in the VSF simulation, per-particle states were
 698 logged from a GPU Niagara Fluids system as particles traversed dedicated measurement volumes
 699 aligned with cross sections (XS 1 and XS 4). The approach combines (i) a thin, axis-aligned
 700 "measurement box" actor positioned at the cross sections (Fig. S-29) and (ii) a GPU → CPU
 701 particle-data export in the Niagara emitter that triggers whenever particles interact with that box
 702 (Fig. S-30).

703 3.9.1 Measurement geometry

704 Each measurement box instance is a Blueprint actor with a Box component defining a rectangular
 705 prism of width W , height H , and thickness h aligned with the local cross-section normal \mathbf{n}
 706 (pointing downstream). The box was positioned so that its mid-plane coincides with the target
 707 cross-sectional station (e.g., XS 4). The Level Blueprint exposes its transform, extents (W , H , h),
 708 and unit normal \mathbf{n} to Niagara via parameters.

709 3.9.2 Niagara-side export

710 The fluid emitter ran on the GPU (Sim Target: GPU). In the *Particle Update* stage, the
 711 following workflow was implemented:

Fig. S- 28. Settings of the Movie Render Queue.

- 712 (i) test particle inclusion in the measurement box,
- 713 (ii) assemble a payload of particle and box attributes, and
- 714 (iii) call the `Export Particle Data` module (Niagara Data Interface Export) when the
- 715 inclusion test is true.

716 The exported per-particle payload comprises simulation `Time`, `ParticleID`, `Pos (x,y,z)`,

717 flow velocity `Vel (u, v, w)`, `BoxID`, width `W`, height `H`, box thickness `L`, and per-particle volume

718 for flux calculations `Vp`. The unique `ParticleID` stems from the Niagara particle ID attribute.

719 3.9.3 CPU-side collection and persistence

720 A companion Blueprint (`MeasurementLogger`) subscribes to the Niagara Data Interface

721 `Export` event and buffers the received payload each frame. The logger tagged each record with

722 the corresponding `BoxID` (`XS 1` or `XS 4`) and wrote comma-separated values (CSV) to disk with

723 headers:

time, id, x, y, z, ux, uy, uz, speed, un, boxid, W, H, L, Vp. (4)

724 Data were written under the project directory, and file rotation occurred per run or per
725 in-simulation minute to keep files manageable.

726 3.10 Offline Rendering Workflow with Movie Render Queue

727 Rather than running the simulation in interactive gameplay mode, frames were rendered deter-
728 ministically with the *Movie Render Queue* (MRQ) in Unreal Engine. MRQ renders Sequencer
729 shots with high-quality sampling and output control while still executing simulation logic per
730 frame. This is the recommended path for offline image-sequence rendering in Unreal Engine 5.4
731 and younger.

732 First, the following setting were made in the Niagara system NS_FluidSim for "offline/anal-
733 ysis" mode:

- 734 • Deactivate auxiliary emitters that are only needed for gameplay (e.g., a secondary FLIP
735 emitter used for interactive effects).
- 736 • In *Particle Spawn*, ensure any "kill on spawn" debug toggles are disabled for analysis
737 runs.
- 738 • In *Particle Update*, enable the *Export Particle Data* module (UNiagaraDataInterfaceExport)
739 so per-particle data are emitted to a Blueprint object each tick; keep any gameplay-only

Fig. S- 29. Measurement box actor used to log particles at a cross section.

Fig. S- 30. Per-particle variables exported when interacting with the XS 4 measurement box: time, ID, position, velocity, speed, normal component Un, box metadata, and particle volume Vp.

740 export toggles (e.g., collision-driven exports) disabled. The export interface sends data
741 every frame to a user-provided object that implements the receive callback.

- 742 • Keep *Kill Particles in Volume* (domain trimming) enabled and positioned at the physical
743 boundaries of the VSF control volume.
- 744 • Boundary and solver options (e.g., a `MinFaceFraction` threshold in the high-precision
745 boundary pass, or a custom "pressure add-on" term in a pressure step) should be set to the
746 same calibrated values used in validation runs; these do not depend on MRQ and remain
747 part of the hydrodynamic model.
- 748 • In FLIP/PIC force, `KillParticles` must be disabled.

749 Second, Blueprint references were modified for offline runs. Specifically, in the Level
750 Blueprint, at `BeginPlay`, the Niagara system's *user* object parameters were connected to analysis
751 actors and gameplay-only wiring was disconnected according to the following workflow:

- 752 1. Use `Set Niagara Variable By String (Object)` to assign the logger/measurement
753 actor to the Niagara user parameter that the export interface reads (e.g., `User.Transfer`
754 `Data`). This makes the logger receive the GPU → CPU particle callbacks when parti-
755 cles are inside the measurement box at the XSs. The Blueprint node is a wrapper of
756 `UNiagaraComponent::SetNiagaraVariableObject`, and it is the correct way to set
757 user object parameters at runtime.
- 758 2. Disconnect or null any gameplay-only object parameters (e.g., `User.FishCollision`)
759 and the related `Cast To BP_FishCharacter/Get Player Character` chain. This
760 ensures the offline job does not depend on a player pawn.
- 761 3. A simple `Sequence` node (as shown) lets you flip between *Offline Rendering* (analysis
762 wiring connected) and *Runtime Simulation* (gameplay wiring connected) by changing
763 which pins are active (see Fig. S-31).

764 MRQ advances the scene deterministically according to the timebase of the shots, while
765 actors still tick normally. By default, actors tick once per frame; a custom minimum tick interval
766 can be specified but is not required for MRQ. For analysis runs, the actor *Tick Interval* was 40 s).

767 Next, MRQ was configured as follows:

- 768 1. Open *Window* → *Cinematics* → *Movie Render Queue*, add the level sequence (or movie
769 shots), and open the *Unsaved Config*. Then select *Temporal AA Test 4k* (see Fig. S-28).
- 770 2. In *Settings*, add *Output, Deferred Rendering* (enabled), and *Anti-Aliasing*. Choose the
771 output format (here: `JPG`) and set the desired pixel resolution directly (e.g., `3840×2160`
772 for 4K). These MRQ settings affect images only and do not change the Niagara export
773 load.
- 774 3. For high-quality anti-aliasing, MRQ supports spatial and temporal sample counts (tempo-
775 ral samples slice the shutter interval into sub-frames). Sample counts appropriate to the
776 computing resources; leave *Frame Step* at 1 to render every simulation frame (here: set to
777 2 in configuration file).
- 778 4. Optional: add *Game Overrides* to suppress UI or force cinematic scalability during render.

779 5. Start the job with *Render (Local)*. The image sequence will be saved to the chosen
780 directory, while the Blueprint logger writes CSV logs as usual.

781 The *BeginPlay* event (see Fig. S-31) triggers a Sequence. The *Offline Rendering* branch
782 sets `User.TransferData` on `NS_FluidSim` to `Self` (the logger/measurement actor) via `Set`
783 `Niagara Variable By String (Object)`. The *Runtime Fish Simulation* wiring (cast to a
784 fish character, pass to `User.FishCollision`, etc.) was disconnected for offline analysis. This
785 isolates the hydrodynamics and logging from player-driven logic while preserving the per-frame
786 export callback.

Fig. S- 31. Level Blueprint wiring for offline rendering: connect `User.TransferData` to the logger actor and disconnect gameplay-only collision wiring (fish character).

787 Finally, the following items were checked, in line with the documentation provided by Epic
788 Games:

- 789 • verify that the *Niagara Export Particle Data* module is enabled in *Particle Update* and
790 points to the same user parameter that was set in Blueprint;
- 791 • confirm the Level Sequence covers the target simulation time window;
- 792 • keep actor Tick at default (per frame) during MRQ renders for frame-accurate logging.

3.11 Permeability Check on Model Parts

For the examination of the impermeability of model parts (e.g., the inflow basin), the velocity value was set to zero. Thus, particles were generated with zero initial velocity and, depending on the simulated gravity, fell vertically downward (Fig. S-32), enabling a visual evaluation of the impermeability of a model part.

Fig. S- 32. Setting the particle velocities to 0 helped to verify the impermeability of the model.

With the particle initialization VELOCITY set to zero, the simulation generated particles a temporary *Spawn Rate* of 10 000. The *Water Height* parameter was left at zero for the permeability test.

To enable fluid interactions with model parts, an *Advanced* tag was created by selecting the model part (*Advanced* appears in the *Details* panel). A new *Collider* element was then added in the *Advanced* tab. By defining the *Collider*, bodies (i.e., model parts) and their interaction with the fluid became enabled in the simulations. In addition, the *Engine Scalability* was set to medium (*Settings > Scalability Group*, cf., Fig. S-33). Otherwise, the MDF would have been incorrectly created.

Fig. S- 33. Adjustment of the Engine Scalability for permeability checks.

The activated *Pivot Point* of the simulation was dragged over model parts to verify their correct interaction with particles and ensure there were no leaks.

3.12 Workflow Summary of a Niagara Blueprint Generation

For integrating the simulation into the Unreal Engine model, the Niagara *Actor* was dragged and positioned in the virtual world with the following parameter settings for the VSF simulation:

- Define the emitter sphere with an initial *SpawnRate* (e.g., 1000), *SpawnOffset*, *SpawnScale*, and *SphereRadius*.
- Set *Num Cells Max Axis* to define the cell size.
- Determine the size of the simulation in X-Y-Z dimensions using *World mesh Extents* in centimeter units. To visualize the boundary, enable the *Show Bounds* options in the

817 Niagara System settings. The dimensions of the box should be slightly larger than the
818 model to be simulated.

- 819 • Check the model permeability following the instructions in Sec. 3.11.

820 After making these settings, a test simulation can be started by enabling the Boolean value
821 *Auto Activate*. However, activating the simulation in *Editor Mode* can lead to low performance,
822 that is, a small number of frames per second (fps). This is why simulations were linked with *User*
823 *Parameters* (see Sec. 3.6) to run the simulation efficiently in real-time *Play Mode* (gameplay).
824 The *Play Mode* is activated by the *Play* button.

825 The spawn sphere character was placed over the 3d model of the VSF by dragging the player
826 start over the 3d model. As a result, the gameplay was actively running the simulation in the
827 virtual world in real-time. Thus, the calibration parameters of the simulation could also be
828 changed in real-time by pressing the defined buttons.

829 4 FISH CHARACTER IMPLEMENTATION

830 4.1 Import Fish with Swimming Animation

831 The *Third Person Template* contains a character, modeled as a human body, which interacts with
832 the model while remaining transparent to the fluid. This design allows for navigating through
833 an ongoing simulation (i.e., gameplay) and observing it from the character's perspective. In this
834 study, the default character was substituted with a fish model, and its behavior was modified
835 accordingly. For this purpose, a *glb* file containing a 3d fish model with motion (swimming)
836 animation was imported. This file was created in Blender.

837 The target fish species for the VSF was juvenile brown trout for which no template was freely
838 available on the *Marketplace* or elsewhere on the internet. As a substitute, a free 3d model of a
839 rainbow trout with swimming animation created in Blender was used. Upon import into Unreal
840 Engine, the *Skeletal Mesh Asset* was changed from the default character (human) to the mesh
841 of the imported fish (Fig. S-34a). The animation was saved separately after import into Unreal
842 Engine and linked via the *Use Animation Asset* option (Fig. S-34b). If a seamless transition
843 between various states (e.g., standing, walking, running) is desired, an *Animation Blueprint* can
844 be created as an alternative to the *Use Animation Asset* option.

845 4.2 Particle-Fish Interactions

846 According to the design conditions of the VSF, the maximum
847 counter-current swimming speed of juvenile trout was assumed to be 1.8 m s^{-1} , and the mean
848 counter-current swimming speed with 1.0 m s^{-1} . Therefore, an interaction between the simulation
849 and the fish character was established such that the fish is repelled by particles moving at a speed
850 exceeding 1.0 m s^{-1} . To this end, the above-described export module of the Niagara System
851 (Sec. 3.8.2) and the *LevelBlueprint* (cf., Sec. 3.8.3) were used. The *LevelBlueprint* requires
852 the *NiagaraCallbackHandler* interface: particle data stored in the *FishCollision* object were
853 transmitted to the Level Blueprint through the interface. This approach established a connection
854 between the fish (cf., function map Fig. S-36b) character and the *ActorBlueprint* for the exchange
855 of particle data.

856 Niagara particle information is received only in the Level Blueprint. Thus, through Class
857 Settings, an interface was implemented for the fish character. In the Level Blueprint, the actor

Fig. S- 34. Import of a fish with (a) adaptation of the Skeletal Mesh Asset, and (b) link setup of the fish characters with the swimming animation.

858 was cast to the Fish class to obtain a reference, and this reference was used to push the fish back
 859 against high-velocity currents. This process established a structured approach for data handling
 860 within the *Niagara Fluids* system, ensuring that the fish character receives the necessary particle
 861 information for accurate interaction with the simulated fluid dynamics.

Fig. S- 35. Node graph for storing particle data in the Level Blueprint.

862 The fish is repelled upon collision with fast-moving particles (exceeding 1.0 m s^{-1}) by
 863 analyzing the *ParticleData* array through a loop and creating an invisible sphere around the
 864 fish. The *CharacterCapsule* was adjusted to match the dimensions of the fish, thus defining the
 865 interaction space between the fish and the particles. The speed of particles within a radius of
 866 0.15 m was compared to the maximum swimming speed of the fish. When the particle velocity

Fig. S- 36. Node graphs of (a) delay to prevent cast failed (No Ref for Fish Character) and (b) calculations for fish pushback in Level Blueprint.

867 exceeded 1.0 m s^{-1} , an impulse was transmitted to the fish, causing it to be repelled. However,
 868 the particles remain unaffected by the collision with the fish character; their speed and direction
 869 do not change.

870 4.3 Hovering of the Fish Character

871 To allow the fish character to traverse the VSF at arbitrary depths rather than only near the
 872 bed, motion along the Z-axis was enabled during play. This was implemented by placing
 873 a *PhysicsVolume* in the *ThirdPersonMap* level that encloses the full water domain of the
 874 VSF (excluding solid walls) and setting its *bWaterVolume* property to *True* (see Fig. S-37).
 875 Upon overlap with this volume, the character's *CharacterMovementComponent* automatically
 876 switches its *MovementMode* (*Swimming State*), under which gravity is not applied and vertical
 877 motion is permitted.

878 Z-axis control was realized using standard input axis mappings and control rotation. While
 879 in *Swimming State*, forward input is resolved relative to the camera pitch so that looking up
 880 yields ascent and looking down yields descent. The character can briefly breach the water
 881 surface; when it exits the water volume, the mode reverts to *Falling*, after which the fish
 882 returns below the surface (cf. Fig. S-38). This configuration enables stable hovering and depth
 883 changes throughout the VSF while remaining decoupled from the *Niagara Fluids* simulation of
 884 the flow field.

Fig. S- 37. The VSF from the perspective of the fish character (a) and setup of the physics volume including character movement (b).

Fig. S- 38. Node graph of the fish controls, with the disconnection for offline rendering (a), and items for movement, repelling, and returning below the water surface (b).

5 OpenFOAM

Mesh-based (Eulerian) 3d hydrodynamic numerical modeling was carried out with the open-source software OpenFOAM (Greenshields 2023) and its multiphase solver *interFoam*. OpenFOAM models fluid motion based on the incompressible, transient, two-phase Navier-Stokes equations coupled with a $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence model (Launder & Sharma 1974, Pourahmadi & Humphrey 1983) along a 3d numerical grid using the finite volume method (FVM). Notably, the $k - \varepsilon$ model was used to model turbulence (turbulent kinetic energy k and dissipation rate ε). The PIMPLE algorithm was applied for coupling of pressure and velocity, which combines the robustness of SIMPLE with the transient accuracy of PISO algorithms.

One of the advantages of using OpenFOAM is that it is ideal for representing complex geometries like the slot VSF. OpenFOAM enables accurate mapping of critical areas by defining precise refinement areas. In addition, OpenFOAM allowed for the application of the Volume-of-Fluid (VOF) method to model boundary condition-free water surface movement. A detailed workflow for setting up an OpenFOAM model for simulating hydrodynamics can be found at <https://hydro-informatics.com/of-intro>, which was adopted in this study to simulate the VSF.

5.1 General Model Setup

The following steps were implemented to create, calibrate, and run the hydrodynamic OpenFOAM simulations:

1. Reviewing and processing input data (e.g., converting data formats).
2. Creating the 3d geometry with Blender.
3. Developing the numerical grid with *SnappyHexMesh*, including the definition of initial and boundary conditions.
4. Conducting test runs to verify the functionality of the model and numerical stability, potentially with local grid refinements within the VSF.
5. Iterative model calibration and validation using the physical model.
6. Warm-up simulation with a cold-started inflow of $0.03 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$.
7. Hot-start simulations of Q_{30} , followed by Q_{∞} , and HQ_{100} .
8. Post-processing of the results for comparison with the Unreal Engine/FLIP model.

5.2 Mesh generation & resolution

The VSF model was imported into Blender as an STL file, where materials were assigned to individual model elements representing construction materials. This Blender model was used for the OpenFOAM and Niagara Fluids simulations. For the OpenFOAM simulation, the Blender model was processed with *SnappyHexMesh* for generating a 3d mesh with (split-)hexahedral elements. Further refinement was carried out in areas of particular interest, such as the slots (cf., Fig. S-39).

Fig. S- 39. Mesh of the OpenFOAM model with refinements in the slots of the VSF.

921 The OpenFOAM mesh was designed to match the spatial resolution of the Niagara Fluids
 922 simulations as closely as possible, with refinement ranging from 0.02 m near the slots to 0.2 m
 923 in the upstream and downstream reaches. A formal mesh-independence study was practically
 924 not feasible because individual simulations required between 1,151 and 2,644 wall-clock hours
 925 (see Tab. 2 in the main paper). Instead, the mesh resolution was evaluated a posteriori for the
 926 mean discharge scenario (Q_{ϕ}) using three diagnostics derived from the converged solution fields.
 927 First, the Courant number remained well below 0.1 across most of the domain; peak values of up
 928 to 0.5 (enforced; see Sec. 5.3) occurred only in the slots, where the mesh was already at its finest
 929 resolution (0.02 m). Second, the velocity-gradient field showed large gradients confined to the
 930 slot shear layers and sharp corners, while coarser upstream and downstream regions exhibited
 931 low gradients, indicating that these areas were not under-resolved. Third, the maximum turbulent
 932 viscosity reached $\nu_t = 3.1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, corresponding to a viscosity ratio $\nu_t/\nu \approx 3.1 \times 10^4$, which
 933 is consistent with turbulent free-surface flow through a complex geometry and does not indicate
 934 anomalously high eddy viscosity that would be symptomatic of insufficient mesh resolution
 935 (Pope 2000). In sum, these diagnostics involve checks of the adopted mesh for cross-model
 936 comparisons, but they cannot replace a mesh convergence study.

937 **5.3 Wall-Function Consistency Constraints on Mesh Variation in the Open-** 938 **FOAM Reference Model**

939 The following paragraphs document why a formal global mesh-refinement study cannot be
 940 performed on the OpenFOAM reference simulation as a refinement of the same model, and
 941 why coarsening cannot be performed without altering the resolved geometry of the slot. At the
 942 used resolution, several wetted wall patches already have y^+ minima below the lower validity
 943 bound of the wall functions in use ($y^+ \approx 30$) at all three discharges. Wall-normal refinement
 944 under the same closure would push more cells into the buffer ($5 < y^+ < 30$) and viscous-
 945 sublayer ($y^+ < 5$) ranges, where the high-Re $k-\varepsilon$ formulation with `kqR/epsilon/nutk` wall
 946 functions is not the appropriate near-wall treatment. Coarsening, in turn, reduces the number
 947 of cells across each slot below the threshold at which the slot is resolved as a flow feature. The
 948 following paragraphs and tables present the y^+ distributions on all wetted solid wall patches
 949 at the three discharges Q_{30} , Q_{ϕ} , and HQ_{100} (Section 5.3.1); the near-wall mesh statistics and
 950 refinement-level configuration produced by `snappyHexMesh` (Section 5.3.2); the wall-function
 951 specification used on each patch (Section 5.3.3); a synthesis of the methodological constraints
 952 (Section 5.3.4); and the verbatim `0/` field definitions for direct verification (Section 5.3.6). Data
 953 are extracted from the simulations (`postProcessing -func yPlus, final timestep`) and from
 954 the `snappyHexMeshDict / blockMeshDict` definitions.

955 5.3.1 y^+ Distributions on wetted wall patches

956 The OpenFOAM model uses wall functions, so we replace the no-slip condition at the wall with
 957 an algebraic relation that imposes a roughness-adapted log-law between the first cell center and
 958 the wall, skipping the viscous sublayer and the buffer layer entirely. So we assume the first cell
 959 center is located in the log-layer, meaning $30 < y^+ < 300\text{--}500$, of the form $u^+ = (1/\kappa) \cdot \ln(E \cdot y^+)^1$,
 960 in which $y^+ < 30$ has no physical meaning because when $y^+ < 5$, $u^+ = y^+$ (linear relation), and
 961 in the buffer ($5 < y^+ < 30$), neither linear nor log profiles apply, so there is no closed form
 962 profile. With OpenFOAM's `nutkRoughWallFunction`, if the solver hits a cell with $y^+ = 0.5$,
 963 the wall function still computes a wall shear stress using a relation that assumes y^+ is in the log
 964 range. The result is a numerical value that the solver accepts without complaining, but that value
 965 is not consistent with the physics of a viscous sublayer. Refining the mesh in the wall-normal
 966 direction reduces the first-cell-center distance, which reduces y^+ proportionally. Thus:

- 967 • A cell currently at $y^+ = 50$ (inside the log range) refined by a factor of 2 moves to $y^+ \approx 25$
 968 (now in the buffer layer, wall function invalid).
- 969 • A cell currently at $y^+ = 5$ (already in the viscous sublayer) refined by a factor of 2 moves
 970 to $y^+ \approx 2.5$ (deeper into the sublayer, wall function still invalid).
- 971 • A cell currently at $y^+ = 0.5$ refined by a factor of 2 moves to $y^+ \approx 0.25$ (still in the sublayer;
 972 the wall function remains invalid, and refinement only becomes meaningful under a switch
 973 to a wall-resolved closure).

974 Thus, for further refinement, we needed to switch to a wall-resolved RANS simulation to resolve
 975 the viscous sublayer all the way to the wall, which would target small y^+ ($y^+ \approx 1$ at the first
 976 cell center). Such a switch would constitute a different model with a different near-wall closure
 977 rather than a cell-size-only refinement of the model setup.

978 On the contrary, coarsening to enable a formal mesh-convergence study would reduce the
 979 number of horizontal cells across each slot to fewer than 5 cells. So the slots are no longer
 980 resolved as a flow feature: the jet shear layer collapses onto a single cell-face, the integrated
 981 mass and momentum flux through the slot becomes mesh-dependent, and the strain-rate field
 982 that drives the $k\text{-}\varepsilon$ turbulence production is set by the discretization rather than by the physics.
 983 Coarsening therefore does not produce a coarser-resolution version of the same model but one
 984 in which a central feature of our study (the slots) is no longer represented. The reasoning
 985 also applies to coarsening of the slot side walls, where the wall-function sampling distance must
 986 remain in the log-law range and currently is located at first-cell-center distances of approximately
 987 0.006 to 0.025 m.

988 The following tables report the minimum, maximum, and mean y^+ on every solid wall patch
 989 wetted at the corresponding discharge. Air and inlet boundaries and patches that remain dry at
 990 all discharges are excluded. Values of y^+_{\min} below 30 are highlighted in bold; these are patches
 991 where part of the boundary already is at or below the lower wall-function validity limit at the
 992 used resolution.

¹ $E \approx 9.8$ is the smooth-wall log-law constant (replaced by an equivalent E^* on rough walls; OpenFOAM's `nutkRoughWallFunction` applies the Cebeci-Bradshaw rough-wall correlation with roughness height k_s (as listed in Tab. S-6) and roughness constant $C_s = 0.5$)

5.3.1.1 Q_{30}

The most relevant patch for the slots in the fishway is `Substratum_fishpass`. Minima are below 1, indicating cells already located in the viscous-sublayer range at the used resolution, while maxima exceed 4000 on the same patches. y^+ therefore varies by several orders of magnitude across wetted boundaries, and a single global wall-normal refinement cannot simultaneously improve validity for the high- y^+ and low- y^+ cells. Any such refinement would push a larger fraction of the wetted boundary into the buffer ($5 < y^+ < 30$) and viscous-sublayer ($y^+ < 5$) ranges, where the high-Re k - ε closure with `kqR/epsilon/nutk` wall functions is no longer the appropriate near-wall treatment.

Tab. S- 1. y^+ statistics on wetted wall patches at Q_{30} . Bold entries indicate $y_{\min}^+ < 30$.

Patch	y_{\min}^+	y_{\max}^+	y_{avg}^+
Edelstahlverkleidung	0.004	4334.07	137.07
Magerbeton	0.860	3964.19	195.57
Magerbeton_- refinement	8.57	662.25	256.16
Stahlbeton_- refinement	4.17	10,138.30	334.38
Stahlbeton_right	0.570	6017.59	151.26
Substratum_fishpass	17.30	7110.03	1226.01
Substratum_final	0.890	5101.01	790.64
Substratum_pt1	0.009	4342.28	232.74
Substratum_weir	0.530	4577.32	237.52

5.3.1.2 Q_{\circ}

y^+ generally increases at Q_{\circ} relative to Q_{30} , but eight of nine wetted patches still show minima below the wall-function lower bound of 30, with several below 1. The wall-function-validity problem at the low- y^+ tail therefore persists at Q_{\circ} despite the higher mean y^+ , and a global wall-normal refinement would push a larger fraction of these tails into the buffer ($5 < y^+ < 30$) and viscous-sublayer ($y^+ < 5$) ranges. The incompatibility with the k - ε closure under standard wall functions is therefore not relieved at Q_{\circ} .

5.3.1.3 HQ_{100}

Five wetted patches retain y^+ minima below the wall-function lower bound of 30 at HQ_{100} (most important: `Substratum_fishpass`), while maxima on the same patches exceed 7000 and reach above 31,000 in the `Stahlbeton_refinement` patch. y^+ therefore spans several orders of magnitude across the wetted boundary even at the flood discharge, and the wall-function-validity problem at the low- y^+ tail is not relieved at HQ_{100} . Refinement under the present closure would aggravate it on the same patches that show the problem at Q_{30} and Q_{\circ} .

5.3.2 Mesh statistics

5.3.2.1 Global statistics

The mesh used for all simulations is summarized in Tab. S-4.

Tab. S- 2. y^+ statistics on wetted wall patches at Q_{\odot} . Bold entries indicate $y_{\min}^+ < 30$.

Patch	y_{\min}^+	y_{\max}^+	y_{avg}^+
Edelstahlverkleidung	0.027	4015.45	196.16
Magerbeton	13.94	8528.85	1141.65
Magerbeton_- refinement	30.79	1566.52	335.58
Stahlbeton_- refinement	3.19	13,613.09	619.46
Stahlbeton_right	2.41	8208.87	353.61
Substratum_fishpass	17.40	7055.43	1197.68
Substratum_final	3.09	5800.17	876.49
Substratum_pt1	0.190	6063.01	439.78
Substratum_weir	0.970	2756.39	312.45

Tab. S- 3. y^+ statistics on wetted wall patches at HQ_{100} . Bold entries indicate $y_{\min}^+ < 30$.

Patch	y_{\min}^+	y_{\max}^+	y_{avg}^+
Edelstahlverkleidung	6.19	26,460.99	875.35
Magerbeton	36.58	9495.85	1685.04
Magerbeton_- refinement	87.13	6092.77	1156.56
Stahlbeton_- refinement	9.27	31,681.08	1343.23
Stahlbeton_right	4.10	18,771.62	1726.92
Substratum_fishpass	16.33	7282.95	1186.59
Substratum_final	34.29	5885.25	1509.61
Substratum_pt1	48.74	11722.00	1022.34
Substratum_weir	0.680	7963.20	1063.22

Tab. S- 4. Global mesh statistics for the OpenFOAM simulations.

Mesh Statistic	Value
Total cells	2,602,274
Hexahedra	2,321,046 (89%)
Polyhedra	230,030 (9%)
Prisms	51,128 (2%)
Min cell volume	$1.62 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^3$ ($\approx 5.5 \text{ mm}$ equiv. edge)
Max cell volume	$1.45 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^3$ ($\approx 24 \text{ cm}$ equiv. edge)
Max aspect ratio	11.26
Max non-orthogonality	65.76° (mean 8.60°)
Max skewness	8.17 (26 of 8.2×10^6 faces)
Domain bounding box, x	2.46–26.69 m
Domain bounding box, y	16.34–106.77 m
Domain bounding box, z	0.13–6.00 m

5.3.2.2 Near-wall cell sizes by region

The base mesh is uniform at 0.20 m (400×600×200 cells over the 80×120×40 m domain). snappyHexMesh refines locally per patch; addLayers is set to false, so no inflation layers are present. The first cell center sits at approximately half the near-wall cell size from the wall.

Refinement-level transitions are controlled by nCellsBetweenLevels = 5; no boundary-layer growth ratio applies because no inflation layers are used. The first-cell-center distance of ≈0.6–2.5 cm on the fishpass substratum is consistent with the order-of-magnitude estimate (≈18 mm at Q_{30}) provided in our earlier correspondence.

Tab. S- 5. Near-wall cell sizes and first-cell-center distances by patch region.

Patch	Refinement Level	Near-Wall Cell Size	First Cell-Center Distance
Substratum_fishpass	2–4	1.25–5 cm	≈0.6–2.5 cm
Substratum_pt1	2–4	1.25–5 cm	≈0.6–2.5 cm
Substratum_weir	2–4	1.25–5 cm	≈0.6–2.5 cm
Substratum_final	2	5 cm	≈2.5 cm
Edelstahlverkleidung	2	5 cm	≈2.5 cm
Magerbeton	2	5 cm	≈2.5 cm
Magerbeton_- refinement	2	5 cm	≈2.5 cm
Stahlbeton_- refinement	2	5 cm	≈2.5 cm
Stahlbeton_right	1	10 cm	≈5 cm
Air patches (Luft_*)	0	20 cm	≈10 cm

5.3.3 Wall-function configuration

The OpenFOAM setup uses a uniform near-wall treatment family across all solid wall patches: nutkRoughWallFunction for the turbulent eddy viscosity, kqRWallFunction for k , and epsilonWallFunction for ε . Roughness heights k_s reflect the surface materials (galvanized steel, lean concrete, reinforced concrete, gravel substratum).

All three wall functions presuppose that the wall-adjacent cell center sits within the log-law range, conventionally $30 \lesssim y^+ \lesssim 300$ –500. The full file definitions (θ /nut, θ /k, θ /epsilon) are reproduced verbatim in Section 5.3.6.

5.3.4 Methodological constraints for mesh size variations

Three observations follow from the above figures:

1. At the applied resolution, several wetted wall patches already have y^+ minima below 30 (and in places below 1) at all three discharges. The mesh is therefore already at, and locally below, the lower validity bound of the wall-function range, which is only justifiable because of the needed resolution in the slots.
2. Wall-normal refinement would shift a larger fraction of first cell centers into the buffer ($5 < y^+ < 30$) and viscous-sublayer ($y^+ < 5$) ranges, where the high-Re k - ε formulation with kqR/epsilon/nutk wall functions is not physically consistent. The refined model would not be a finer-mesh version of the OpenFOAM model; it would be a different model with a different near-wall treatment (low-Re or wall-resolved RANS).

Tab. S- 6. Wall-function assignments and roughness heights k_s by patch and field.

Patch / Field	Wall Function	k_s (m)
Edelstahlverkleidung	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.0001
Magerbeton	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.003
Magerbeton_ refinement	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.003
Stahlbeton_ refinement	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.0052
Stahlbeton_right	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.0052
Stahlblech	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.00015
Substratum_fishpass	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.15
Substratum_final	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.15
Substratum_pt1	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.15
Substratum_weir	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.15
Substratum_ amphibienweg	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.15
Inlet_box	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.0001
Luft_sides, Luft_ top_init	nutkRoughWallFunction	0.0052
k (all walls)	kqRWallFunction	–
ε (all walls)	epsilonWallFunction	–

1046 3. Coarsening, in turn, degrades the geometric representation of the slot (refinement levels
1047 2–4 on Substratum_fishpass, Substratum_pt1, and Substratum_weir, with first-
1048 cell-center distances of 0.6–2.5 cm), which is the central feature of the study. Coarsening
1049 also is not a mesh-only change.

1050 The used mesh is therefore best characterized as application-oriented: configured to remain in
1051 the wall-function validity range across as much of the wetted boundary as feasible given the slot
1052 geometry, the roughness scales of the bed and wall materials, and the available computational
1053 resources.

1054 5.3.5 Quality checks

1055 The following checks were performed and are reported here for completeness:

- 1056 • Patch-resolved y^+ statistics at used resolution for all three discharges (Section 5.3.1).
- 1057 • Mesh-quality diagnostics: max non-orthogonality 65.76° (mean 8.60°), max aspect ratio
1058 11.26, max skewness 8.17 on 26 of 8.2×10^6 faces (Section 5.3.2).
- 1059 • Cross-comparison against the physical-flume reference data at four transects and three
1060 discharges as documented in the manuscript.
- 1061 • Cross-comparison against the Niagara Fluids PIC/FLIP solver, for which a three-level
1062 mesh-refinement check (0.096, 0.048, 0.024 m) is reported in the manuscript.

1063 5.3.6 OpenFOAM 0/ field definitions

1064 The following blocks reproduce the used 0/nut, 0/k, and 0/epsilon files used in all three
 1065 discharge simulations. They are included for direct verification of the wall-function setup
 1066 summarized in Section 5.3.3.

1067 5.3.6.1 0/nut

```

1068 dimensions      [0 2 -1 0 0 0 0];
1069 internalField    uniform 0;
1070
1071 boundaryField
1072 {
1073     Edelstahlverkleidung
1074     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.0001; Cs uniform
1075       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1076     Inlet
1077     { type calculated; value uniform 0; }
1078     Inlet_box
1079     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.0001; Cs uniform
1080       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1081     Luft_sides
1082     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.0052; Cs uniform
1083       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1084     Luft_top
1085     { type calculated; value uniform 0; }
1086     Luft_top_init
1087     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.0052; Cs uniform
1088       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1089     Magerbeton
1090     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.003; Cs uniform
1091       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1092     Magerbeton_refinement
1093     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.003; Cs uniform
1094       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1095     Outlet
1096     { type calculated; value uniform 0; }
1097     Stahlbeton_refinement
1098     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.0052; Cs uniform
1099       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1100     Stahlbeton_right
1101     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.0052; Cs uniform
1102       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1103     Stahlblech
1104     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.00015; Cs uniform
1105       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1106     Substratum_amphibienweg
1107     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.15; Cs uniform
1108       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1109     Substratum_final

```

```

1110     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.15;    Cs uniform
1111       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1112     Substratum_fishpass
1113     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.15;    Cs uniform
1114       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1115     Substratum_pt1
1116     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.15;    Cs uniform
1117       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1118     Substratum_weir
1119     { type nutkRoughWallFunction; Ks uniform 0.15;    Cs uniform
1120       0.5; value uniform 0; }
1121 }

```

1122 5.3.6.2 ν/k

```

1123 dimensions      [0 2 -2 0 0 0 0];
1124 internalField   uniform 1.5e-04;
1125
1126 boundaryField
1127 {
1128     Inlet      { type fixedValue; intensity 0.05; value
1129                 $internalField; }
1130     Outlet     { type inletOutlet; inletValue $internalField; value
1131                 $internalField; }
1132     Luft_top   { type inletOutlet; inletValue $internalField; value
1133                 $internalField; }
1134     ".*"       { type kqRWallFunction; value $internalField; }
1135 }

```

1136 5.3.6.3 ν/ϵ

```

1137 dimensions      [0 2 -3 0 0 0 0];
1138 internalField   uniform 1.38e-06;
1139
1140 boundaryField
1141 {
1142     Inlet      { type fixedValue; value $internalField; }
1143     Outlet     { type inletOutlet; inletValue $internalField; value
1144                 $internalField; }
1145     Luft_top   { type inletOutlet; inletValue $internalField; value
1146                 $internalField; }
1147     ".*"       { type epsilonWallFunction; value $internalField; }
1148 }

```

1149 5.4 Discretization

1150 A first-order implicit Euler scheme was applied for time discretization. Spatial discretization
 1151 used bounded second-order schemes: a linear upwind scheme for momentum, upwind schemes

1152 for k and ε , and a TVD scheme based on the van Leer flux limiter for the volume fraction to
1153 maintain a sharp free surface.

1154 The pressure equation was solved with a geometric-algebraic multigrid (GAMG) solver,
1155 and velocity and turbulence equations with the preconditioned biconjugate gradient stabilized
1156 (PBiCGStab) method. Convergence at each timestep was enhanced by reducing residuals for
1157 velocity, pressure, and turbulence quantities below 10^{-5} – 10^{-6} . Wall roughness effects related to
1158 structural elements were represented through wall functions incorporating empirically defined
1159 roughness heights (k_s).

1160 5.5 Boundary conditions

1161 The model had four types of boundary conditions: *atmosphere*, *inlet*, *outflow*, and *walls*. The
1162 atmosphere boundary condition was essential for the VOF method, which served to simulate
1163 two-phase flow (air and water). To replicate the steady-state discharges listed in the main paper,
1164 a *flowRateInletVelocity* boundary condition was defined at the inlet, specifying the discharge
1165 (inflow) only. At the outlet, a discharge condition for free outflow was set, with an undefined
1166 water depth, corresponding to a model degree of freedom. Only for the flood discharge scenario
1167 (HQ_{100}), a stage-discharge relationship was necessary at the outflow to ensure model stability.

1168 The atmospheric pressure for the free water level in the model was assigned using a mixed
1169 (*pressureInletOutletVelocity*) and a Dirichlet (*totalPressure*) boundary condition.

1170 Wall friction was set according to Nikuradse (Nikuradse 1933). To define friction zones, a
1171 *nutkRoughWallFunction* was applied to all walls. The roughness heights (k_s) were determined
1172 based on the technical and natural elements included in the VSF design. The assigned roughness
1173 heights for the materials used in the planned VSF were implemented as listed in Tab. 7, after
1174 iterative calibration with the physical model.

1175 5.6 Calibration & Validation

1176 The numerical model was calibrated regarding water depths observed in the OpenFOAM model
1177 and physical lab flume (cf., measurement profiles in the main paper) by adapting the roughness
1178 (friction) heights listed in Tab. 7. For the substrate, the final results corresponded to approxi-
1179 mately three times its D_{90} (i.e., the grain diameter that is larger than 90% of the sediment mass).
1180 The calibration ensured no substantial deviation between the numerical and physical models
1181 occurred. The approach taken in this study differed from traditional model calibration and
1182 validation methods that rely on field data from multiple observation periods, as such data was
1183 not available for the planned VSF. Instead, the structure optimization process was based on the
1184 data products generated by the initial state models to iteratively make any necessary adjustments
1185 to the friction values.

1186 5.7 Numerical Schemes and Solver Settings

1187 Time integration used a first-order implicit Euler scheme. Pressure–velocity coupling fol-
1188 lowed the PIMPLE algorithm, a merged PISO–SIMPLE scheme, with two pressure corrector
1189 steps, no non-orthogonal correctors, and the momentum predictor disabled. The convective
1190 term in the momentum equation was discretized with a second-order *linearUpwind* scheme,
1191 while the VOF phase fraction was advected with an interface-compression van Leer scheme.

Tab. S- 7. Calibrated roughness heights (friction values) used in the OpenFOAM simulation.

Material	Roughness height k_s (m)
Lean concrete	0.003
Grass	0.2
Grass paving blocks	0.02
Reinforced concrete	0.0052
Substrate ($3 \times D_{90} = 0.032$ m)	0.15
Paving stone	0.04

1192 The turbulent quantities k and ε were discretized with a first-order upwind scheme. Gradi-
 1193 ent terms used second-order central differencing (`Gauss linear`), and Laplacian terms were
 1194 discretized with a second-order central scheme including non-orthogonal correction (`Gauss
 1195 linear corrected`). The modified pressure p_{rgh} was solved with a GAMG preconditioner
 1196 with an absolute tolerance of 5×10^{-9} , and velocity and turbulence quantities were solved with a
 1197 symmetric Gauss–Seidel smoother with an absolute tolerance of 10^{-6} . The VOF phase fraction
 1198 was solved with a MULES-corrected `smoothSolver`, where MULES (acronym for "Multidi-
 1199 mensional Universal Limiter for Explicit Solution") is a flux limiter that ensures boundedness
 1200 of the phase fraction between 0 and 1. The maximum Courant number was set to 0.5, while the
 1201 maximum interface Courant number was limited to 0.25 to maintain sharp interface resolution
 1202 during VOF advection.

6 PHYSICAL EXPERIMENTS (LAB FLUME)

6.1 Purpose & Elements

The VSF modeled in this study did not yet exist in the modeling phase. However, the original project required a high degree of certainty regarding both fish passage and flood safety. Notably, the planned VSF crosses under a four-lane highway, a high-voltage transmission line, a tramway, and a metro line. The structure is covered with a concrete ceiling that should not be subjected to pressurized flow conditions at any flood discharge, as it is difficult to access once constructed. To ensure this, the physical model was built and used to test the reliability of the numerically modeled flood safety. The physical model elements are shown in Fig. S-40, and Fig. S-41 shows the inflow region of the 1:3-scaled physical lab model of the slot VSF (Scolari et al. 2024).

The model was built in the Hydraulic Laboratory of the Institute for Modelling Hydraulic and Environmental Systems at the University of Stuttgart, located in Stuttgart, Germany. Construction was completed in 2022, and the flume tests were conducted from April 2022 through July 2024.

Fig. S- 40. CAD model of the physical lab model of the VSF at 1:3 geometric scale, built in the Hydraulic Laboratory of the Institute for Modelling Hydraulic and Environmental Systems at the University of Stuttgart, Germany.

6.2 Scaling

Froude similitude applies to the dimensions and results of the physical lab model at a geometric scale of $\lambda = 1 : 3$. The resulting kinematic and volumetric scales are listed in Tab. S-8, according to Yalin 1971 and Barenblatt 1996.

Fig. S- 41. Inflow section of the physical lab model of the VSF at 1:3 geometric scale.
Tab. S- 8. Scales of the physical flume experiments according to Froude similitude.

Parameter	Scale	Units
Length (geometric)	$\lambda = 1 : 3$	m
Area	$\lambda^2 = 1 : 9$	m ²
Time	$\lambda^{0.5} = 1 : 3^{0.5}$	s
Velocity	$\lambda^{0.5} = 1 : 3^{0.5}$	m s ⁻¹
Volumetric flow	$\lambda^{2.5} = 1 : 3^{2.5}$	m ³ s ⁻¹

6.3 Calibration

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The physical model was iteratively calibrated based on the OpenFOAM model by adjusting the downstream boundary for each simulated discharge (at model scales, see Tab. S-8). The downstream boundary of the physical model consisted of an outflow weir that was modified until its height generated backwater that corresponded to the normal flow conditions in the hypothetically extended downstream channel of the numerical model. While the effects of the downstream outflow weir level were noticeable up to the most downstream basin of the VSF, these effects were not observed in the more upstream basins. This lack of effect was due to each basin's dividing wall imposing a hydraulic control section. In these control sections, the Froude number was unity or higher, preventing the propagation of backwater in the upstream direction. However, as a consequence of this calibration procedure, the water levels in the flood evacuation channel, downstream of the weir were influenced by the OpenFOAM results. Therefore, the most downstream water depth measurement of the physical lab flume and the OpenFOAM simulations were imposed to be identical. No other model parameters were calibrated, as the scaled gravel and construction materials were similar in the OpenFOAM and physical lab models (Scolari et al. 2024).

1237 **6.4 Measurement Devices & Data**

1238 The data were recorded with ultrasonic sensors and a velocity profiler. The ultrasonic sensors
1239 (type: PEPPERL+FUCHS UB500-18GM75-U-V15) recorded voltage responses that were con-
1240 verted to water depth using linear interpolation curves and by subtracting the distance to the
1241 channel bed. In-house software was used for post-processing of the voltage signals. A Nortek
1242 Vectrino profiler for acoustic Doppler velocimetry (ADV) was used to record the velocity of
1243 the 3d flow field. The device was set to 100 Hz recordings and the Vectrino II software was
1244 used for post-processing of the recorded signals. However, due to device failure, narrow walls,
1245 and low water depth, ADV measurements could not be made reliably (e.g., with an acceptably
1246 high signal-to-noise ratio, $SNR > 20$) during all experiments. Therefore, the ADV flow ve-
1247 locity measurements were derived from different experimental runs and corrected for discharge
1248 fluctuations. The cross-section-averaged flow velocity was back-calculated from water depth
1249 measurements at XS 1 and 4 for all discharges, and at XS 2 and 3 only for Q30, because the
1250 repartitioning of the discharge between the VSF and the flood bypass could not be quantified in
1251 the laboratory flume. All measurement data, including pictures and videos of the experiments,
1252 are available at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12756966> (Schwindt 2024).

1253 **6.5 Qualitative Post-processing with OpenCV**

1254 A qualitative comparison by estimating surface motion from inlet and slot videos of the HQ_{100}
1255 was performed using the OpenCV library (Bradski 2000) and scikit-image (van der Walt et al.
1256 2014). Specifically, Farnebäck 2003 optical flow (`calcOpticalFlowFarneback`) was used to
1257 compute a dense, per-pixel displacement field between consecutive grayscale frames by locally
1258 approximating image neighborhoods with quadratic polynomials, yielding sub-pixel horizontal
1259 motion vectors (u, v) . The framewise fields were temporally averaged to reduce noise, and the
1260 implementation is provided in Schwindt 2025. The resulting streamplots (Fig. 3 in the main
1261 paper) should be interpreted as relative velocities (pixels per frame) rather than absolute values
1262 because no geometric calibration was available.

7 FLOW VELOCITY & WATER DEPTH DATA

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1264 Red error bars in Fig. 5 show 95% confidence intervals computed from the 40 s time series at
 1265 each cross-section. They quantify temporal variability within the 40 s window for each of the
 1266 three steady-discharge scenarios. In the numerical simulations, this variability reflects residual
 1267 numerical variability and excludes parametric uncertainty such as roughness. In the physical
 1268 flume experiments, variability in the 40 s averages arises from flow oscillations and instrument
 1269 precision.

Tab. S- 9. Maxima

FLOW VELOCITY (m s ⁻¹)		Discharge scenario		
XS		Q_{30}	Q_{∞}	HQ_{100}
XS 1	U max (UE)	1.0840	0.9250	1.8100
XS 1	U std (UE)	0.2610	0.2370	0.3820
XS 1	U max (OF)	1.0980	1.1150	2.5120
XS 1	U std (OF)	0.0120	0.0010	0.0180
XS 1	U max (lab)	N.A.	0.6926	1.2820
XS 1	U std (lab)	N.A.	0.1578	0.4127
XS 2	U max (UE)	1.2470	1.7460	1.7640
XS 2	U std (UE)	0.3080	0.4990	0.4480
XS 2	U max (OF)	1.2690	1.4240	1.2850
XS 2	U std (OF)	0.0160	0.0010	0.0120
XS 2	U max (lab)	1.1792	1.6579	1.8647
XS 2	U std (lab)	0.2382	0.3106	0.4837
XS 3	U max (UE)	0.8590	1.7930	1.8230
XS 3	U std (UE)	0.1810	0.4950	0.4860
XS 3	U max (OF)	1.3880	1.5360	1.3600
XS 3	U std (OF)	0.0250	0.0010	0.0040
XS 3	U max (lab)	1.0656	1.6188	1.3214
XS 3	U std (lab)	0.1660	0.2318	0.2781
XS 4	U max (UE)	0.3410	0.4050	0.9410
XS 4	U std (UE)	0.0810	0.0780	0.1580
XS 4	U max (OF)	0.3540	0.5000	0.7280
XS 4	U std (OF)	0.0030	0.0010	0.0250
XS 4	U max (lab)	0.2305	0.9210	1.2009
XS 4	U std (lab)	0.0396	0.0686	0.2233
WATER DEPTH (m)		Discharge scenario		
XS	Q_{30}	Q_{∞}	HQ_{100}	
XS 1	h max (UE)	0.1570	0.2800	0.5300
XS 1	h std (UE)	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100
XS 1	h max (OF)	0.1600	0.3040	0.5100
XS 1	h std (OF)	0.0005	0.0003	0.0040
XS 1	h max (lab)	0.1471	0.2793	0.4581

Continued on next page

Tab. S- 9. Maxima

FLOW VELOCITY (m s ⁻¹)		Discharge scenario		
XS 1	h std (lab)	0.0036	0.0066	0.0100
XS 2	h max (UE)	0.1200	0.3200	0.5950
XS 2	h std (UE)	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100
XS 2	h max (OF)	0.2580	0.3960	0.6420
XS 2	h std (OF)	0.0007	0.0004	0.0010
XS 2	h max (lab)	0.2500	0.3900	0.6300
XS 2	h std (lab)	0.0061	0.0091	0.0144
XS 3	h max (UE)	0.1000	0.3250	0.6300
XS 3	h std (UE)	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100
XS 3	h max (OF)	0.2450	0.4140	0.6650
XS 3	h std (OF)	0.0008	0.0005	0.0006
XS 3	h max (lab)	0.2500	0.3900	0.6400
XS 3	h std (lab)	0.0058	0.0089	0.0140
XS 4	h max (UE)	0.2620	0.3380	0.8760
XS 4	h std (UE)	0.0100	0.0100	0.0100
XS 4	h max (OF)	0.2660	0.3840	0.8510
XS 4	h std (OF)	0.0004	0.0004	0.0005
XS 4	h max (lab)	0.2700	0.3600	0.8400
XS 4	h std (lab)	0.0061	0.0077	0.0183

Tab. S- 10. Averages

FLOW VELOCITY (m s ⁻¹)		Discharge scenario		
XS		Q_{30}	Q_{∞}	HQ_{100}
XS 1	U mean (UE)	0.7007	0.6026	1.4650
XS 1	U std (UE)	0.2650	0.2345	0.3800
XS 1	U mean (OF)	0.6956	0.5165	16179
XS 1	U std (OF)	0.0120	0.0010	0.0180
XS 1	U mean (lab)	0.7691	0.6124	18669
XS 1	U std (lab)	0.0154	0.0122	0.0373
XS 2	U mean (UE)	0.5731	0.8989	0.9892
XS 2	U std (UE)	0.3020	0.4900	0.4160
XS 2	U mean (OF)	0.2120	0.2100	0.3280
XS 2	U std (OF)	0.0160	0.0010	0.0120
XS 2	U mean (lab)	0.2087	N.A.	N.A.
XS 2	U std (lab)	0.0042	N.A.	N.A.
XS 3	U mean (UE)	0.4749	0.9914	10073
XS 3	U std (UE)	0.1770	0.4890	0.4500
XS 3	U mean (OF)	0.2000	0.1610	0.3820
XS 3	U std (OF)	0.0250	0.0010	0.0040

Continued on next page

Tab. S- 10. Averages

FLOW VELOCITY (m s ⁻¹)		Discharge scenario		
XS 3	U mean (lab)	0.2087	N.A.	N.A.
XS 3	U std (lab)	0.0042	N.A.	N.A.
XS 4	U mean (UE)	0.2595	0.3122	0.7195
XS 4	U std (UE)	0.0790	0.0770	0.1580
XS 4	U mean (OF)	0.2216	0.2349	0.4607
XS 4	U std (OF)	0.0030	0.0010	0.0250
XS 4	U mean (lab)	0.2149	0.2680	0.4666
XS 4	U std (lab)	0.0043	0.0054	0.0093

8 BACKGROUND ON CALIBRATION PARAMETERS IN UNREAL ENGINE

8.1 Calibration Parameter Rationales

8.1.1 MinFaceFraction

While MinFaceFraction was set to a small value of 0.04 for the two lower flow scenarios, the shallow water in the slots barely filled portions of mesh cells, making it easy for the solver to "leak" flow downstream. At HQ_{100} , a larger fluid fraction was required to open flow paths, which was achieved by raising MinFaceFraction to 0.20.

8.1.2 PIC/FLIP Ratio

In the low-flow (Q_{30}) scenario, the PIC-FLIP simulations performed poorly in the slots (XS 2 and XS 3, see Figs. 4 and 5 in the paper). These issues can be mainly attributed to the number of parcels-per-cell, the geometrical resolution of the simulation, and how parcels are advected through the model. Specifically, the GPU implementation of PIC-FLIP in Niagara maintains nearly diffusion-free Lagrangian advection, so when velocity gradients are mild the parcel set remains approximately homogeneous. In highly disturbed, sharp-edged layouts such as the VSF, however, the jet from each slot creates strong convergence toward the high-speed core and divergence within the adjacent flow zones, causing parcels to crowd the jet while slowly leaving eddies starved of samples (Brackbill et al. 1988).

Because FLIP updates the velocity of each parcel using only the incremental change between timesteps computed on the mesh, it largely avoids the repeated interpolation–averaging of the full velocity field and therefore introduces much less numerical diffusion than a pure PIC update. In contrast, a pure PIC update (i.e., PIC/FLIP Ratio of zero) overwrites parcel velocities each timestep with the interpolated mesh velocity, which is more dissipative. Accordingly, the PIC/FLIP Ratio optimum was found close to its maximum (i.e., a nearly pure FLIP update) to preserve jet momentum in the slots, shear layers, and pool-scale circulation pattern. Equation 5 shows the implementation of the PIC/FLIP Ratio $\beta \in [0, 1]$ as the FLIP weight in the velocity update.

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{parcel}}^{n+1} = (1 - \beta) \mathbf{u}_{\text{mesh} \rightarrow \text{parcel}}^{n+1} + \beta \left(\mathbf{u}_{\text{parcel}}^n + \Delta \mathbf{u}_{\text{mesh} \rightarrow \text{parcel}} \right) \quad (5)$$

where superscripts n and $n+1$ denote time levels, the subscript "parcel" is the Lagrangian parcel velocity, "mesh" is the Eulerian mesh velocity, "mesh \rightarrow parcel" indicates interpolation from mesh to the parcel location, and $\Delta \mathbf{u}_{\text{mesh} \rightarrow \text{parcel}} = \left(\mathbf{u}_{\text{mesh}}^{n+1} - \mathbf{u}_{\text{mesh}}^n \right)_{\text{interpolated}}$. Thus, with $\beta = 0.98$ (i.e., $\sim 98\%$ FLIP and $\sim 2\%$ PIC), numerical diffusion was substantially reduced relative to a pure PIC update (i.e., advective dissipation was limited).

8.1.3 PressureAddon

The custom PressureAddon can be viewed as a soft, empirical surrogate for strict incompressibility. In the incompressible OpenFOAM projection, a Poisson problem is solved so that the corrected velocity field is divergence-free (up to solver tolerance), enforcing continuity and preventing spurious compression along convergent streamlines. By contrast, Niagara's PIC-FLIP implementation performs an approximate pressure projection on a coarser render mesh

1308 (here with multiplier = 1; cf. Tab. 1 in the main paper) with thresholded face activation (via
 1309 `MinFaceFraction`) and parcel-mesh transfers that can introduce residual divergence and vol-
 1310 ume error, especially in the 98%-FLIP-dominated simulation. While the `PressureAddon` term
 1311 improves continuity, it remains an empirical calibration term rather than a physical pressure, so
 1312 it had to be co-calibrated with `MinFaceFraction` and `Spawn Rate` to avoid over-stiffening the
 1313 flow or damping physically relevant shear.

1314 The identical `PressureAddon` setting of 400 for Q_{30} and Q_{∞} indicated a baseline repulsive
 1315 offset sufficient to prevent FLIP-induced parcel locking at sharp edges while avoiding artificial
 1316 head loss. At these discharges, locking was triggered primarily in sparsely parcel-populated
 1317 regions and at corners when parcels crowded along preferential streamlines. The 400 value
 1318 counteracted residual compressibility without erasing jet coherence. Under HQ_{100} , the much
 1319 larger parcel number and higher local velocities intensified convergence and packing in the slots,
 1320 amplifying locking and biasing the mass flux (visually, producing flocculation-like clumps).
 1321 Raising `PressureAddon` to 1000 supplied a stronger repulsive impulse, restoring effective
 1322 continuity (reducing residual divergence), stabilizing the free surface, and allowing more realistic
 1323 backwater formation despite the near-pure FLIP blend. The trade-off (i.e., modest additional
 1324 numerical head loss) was addressed mainly by setting `MinFaceFraction` to 0.20 at HQ_{100} (i.e.,
 1325 face filling) rather than by larger pressure offsets.

1326 **8.1.4 Spawn Rate**

1327 The `Spawn Rate` calibrations corresponded to sublinear scaling of parcel injection, e.g. in-
 1328 creasing discharge from $Q_{30} = 0.060 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to $Q_{\infty} = 0.13 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (2.25x increase) corre-
 1329 sponds with `Spawn Rate` increasing from 2300 to 4700 (2.04x increase). From Q_{∞} to HQ_{100}
 1330 ($1.0 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), discharge increased by a factor of 7.41 while `Spawn Rate` increased by a factor
 1331 of 5.96 (4700→28000). The implied mean parcel density (`Spawn Rate`/ Q , parcels per m^3),
 1332 therefore decreased with discharge: $\sim 3.83 \times 10^4$ at Q_{30} , $\sim 3.48 \times 10^4$ at Q_{∞} , and 2.80×10^4 at
 1333 HQ_{100} . This monotonic decline is intentional and desirable. Under a 98%-FLIP-dominated
 1334 simulation, low flows are most prone to undersampling of the free surface and partial face
 1335 filling. Keeping the sampling density per unit higher at small discharge improved volume
 1336 representation and mitigated too-facile leakage effects through barely wetted faces (even with
 1337 `MinFaceFraction` = 0.04 at low flows). At flood stages, the flow was energetic and well pop-
 1338 ulated, so maintaining the same parcel sampling density per unit would explode parcel counts,
 1339 cause crowding in slots, and amplify locking and divergence at sharp edges.

1340 The optimal `Spawn Rate` of 28,000 at HQ_{100} reflects a compromise with enough parcels to
 1341 preserve jet coherence and backwater formation, yet not so many as to trigger undesired packing.
 1342 This choice is paired with `MinFaceFraction` = 0.20 and a stronger `PressureAddon` = 1000,
 1343 which help enforce continuity as `Spawn Rate` was throttled per unit discharge. Thus, high-flow
 1344 stability was achieved by shifting from more parcels to smarter constraints, notably, a modestly
 1345 reduced sampling density plus stricter face activation and a larger anti-locking pressure offset.
 1346 On the contrary, at Q_{30} and Q_{∞} , maintaining elevated `Spawn Rate` (2300 and 4700, respectively)
 1347 stabilized free surface and pool volumes (although not optimally) without excessive reliance on
 1348 the artificial `PressureAddon`, consistent with the lower `MinFaceFraction` = 0.04.

1349 **8.1.5 Sequence Display Rate**

1350 Although `Sequence Display Rate` is nominally a rendering control, in the offline workflow
 1351 it couples to Niagara's update loop via the per-frame timestep and substepping, and thus altered

1352 the rendering of fluid properties. At Q_{30} and Q_{∞} the Sequence Display Rate optimum
1353 of 240 fps (frames per second; i.e., small Δt) reduced aliasing of free-surface dynamics, and
1354 therefore, mitigated burst-induced clustering without requiring excessive PressureAddon (400).
1355 In contrast, HQ_{100} demanded far more compute per frame (pressure projection, collisions,
1356 neighbor queries) due to the large Spawn Rate (28,000) and higher velocity. Dropping the
1357 display rate to 120 fps increased the per-frame wall-clock time budget, allowing the solver to
1358 complete the projection passes, collisions, and stabilize the surface. While the larger Δt at
1359 120 fps increased per-frame parcel quantity and could exacerbate packing at sharp edges, this
1360 was counterbalanced by MinFaceFraction = 0.20 and higher PressureAddon = 1000, which
1361 limited spurious compressibility and parcel locking in the slots.

1362 8.1.6 Roughness

1363 A departure from typical calibration in hydraulic engineering is that the wall-roughness param-
1364 eter was not tuned in this study. The VSF walls are smooth, cast concrete; for flows where the
1365 water depth greatly exceeds the representative roughness height, roughness effects on the liquid
1366 core are secondary. This assumption is consistent with hydraulically smooth to transitionally
1367 rough regimes expected for smooth concrete (typical k_s in the mm range). In more natural
1368 settings with coarser beds or macro-topography, roughness becomes a first-order control and
1369 should be modeled (or even resolved) explicitly.

1370 In OpenFOAM, wall roughness was specified as the Nikuradse equivalent sand-grain rough-
1371 ness height, k_s implemented by the nutkRoughWallFunction rough-wall functions. For
1372 smooth concrete $k_s = 0.003$ m was prescribed, following [Nikuradse 1933](#).

1373 Unreal Engine's Niagara Fluids (PIC-FLIP) system does not expose a wall-function rough-
1374 ness parameter. Instead, roughness must be represented through collision interfaces and/or
1375 custom near-wall momentum sinks. In practice, three complementary options exist to account
1376 for wall roughness: (1) geometry-resolved roughness, that is, modeling explicit roughness el-
1377 ements (e.g., cobbles, sills, wood) so their SDFs contribute to the collider used by PIC-FLIP
1378 simulations; (2) enable Collide Against for relevant static meshes and/or the landscape so the
1379 simulation couples to mesh (or GDFs), optionally using GPU ray-traced collisions for smaller
1380 features; and (3) implementing a shallow wall function by adding a local damping (quadratic
1381 drag) within a few mesh cells of the boundary via Simulation Stages or custom HLSL, and
1382 calibrating its coefficient to match a target k_s (or an equivalent Manning's coefficient).

1383 For geometry-resolved roughness, the mesh/GDFs should include the landscape and any
1384 instanced microtopography so the collider generates form drag. This requires sufficiently refined
1385 SDFs and mesh resolution (high voxel density). For modeled (subgrid) roughness, Collide
1386 Against can be used to couple the liquid to tagged static meshes and the landscape via distance
1387 fields. GPU ray-traced collisions may reduce aliasing for small features. For subgrid momentum
1388 sinks, a depth-limited quadratic drag $-C_f |\mathbf{u}| \mathbf{u}$ applied near the bed and walls can be calibrated
1389 to reproduce the intended k_s (or a given Manning's coefficient), where C_f represents a drag
1390 coefficient.

1391 8.2 Considerations for Turbulence Models in Niagara Fluids

1392 Within Niagara Fluids PIC-FLIP Grid3D, a practical large-eddy closure is tangible by computing
1393 the resolved strain-rate tensor from cell-centered velocities and adding an eddy viscosity during
1394 the velocity update. Consistent subgrid particle dispersion can be introduced via stochastic

1395 displacement while leaving the pressure projection unchanged to preserve mass. Such additions
1396 remain substantial work and require extensive validation. Finally, mass-conservation corrections
1397 such as implicit incompressible SPH (IISPH-FLIP) have been proposed for graphics solvers, but
1398 their memory cost grows with parcel count, which limits adoption in real-time engines ([Cornelis
1399 et al. 2014](#)).

Additional Notation

The following symbols are additionally (or differently) used in the supplemental materials:

Co	=	Courant number (–)
D_{90}	=	grain size where 90% are finer (m)
fps	=	frames per second
$\mathbf{n}(x, y)$	=	landscape unit normal (–)
$\mathbf{p} = (x, y, z)$	=	particle world position (m)
\mathbf{u}	=	particle velocity vector (m s ⁻¹)
$u_n = \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n}$	=	normal velocity (m s ⁻¹)
x, y, z	=	world coordinates (m)
$z_L(x, y)$	=	landscape elevation/height (m)
β	=	PIC/FLIP Ratio (–);
$\Delta\zeta$	=	penetration–correction step length (m)

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